

NONLOCAL FREE BOUNDARY MINIMAL SURFACES

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ABSTRACT. We introduce the nonlocal analogue of the classical free boundary minimal hypersurfaces in an open domain Ω of \mathbb{R}^n as the (boundaries of) critical points of the fractional perimeter $\text{Per}_s(\cdot, \Omega)$ with respect to inner variations leaving Ω invariant. We deduce the Euler–Lagrange equations and prove a few surprising features, such as the existence of critical points without boundary and a strong volume constraint in Ω for unbounded hypersurfaces. Moreover, we investigate stickiness properties and regularity across the boundary.

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1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. **Nonlocal free boundary minimal surfaces.** The notion of “free boundary minimal surfaces” arises quite naturally in many problems of physical interest. While an area-minimising surface is typically a surface that minimises area for given boundary data (producing surfaces with zero mean curvature that attach at a prescribed curve along the boundary), in the free boundary case the boundary of the surface is not fixed, and it can “float” to adjust itself in order to minimise the surface area subject to certain constraints. For example, a droplet in a container (or a cell membrane in a biological organism) tends to

minimise surface tension for a given volume: in this case, the boundary of the droplet is not prescribed and forms a contact angle with the container which is of practical importance.

From the mathematical point of view, the analysis of free boundary minimal surfaces dates back to Richard Courant [Cou40], who considered the problem of minimising the area when the boundaries are “free to move on prescribed manifolds” and showed that the minimal surface obtained in this way meets the prescribed manifold orthogonally.

More precisely, free boundary minimal hypersurfaces in a domain Ω are defined as critical points of the area functional with respect to variations supported up to the boundary of Ω , generated by a flow that leaves $\partial\Omega$ invariant. There is a vast literature related to free boundary minimal surfaces, with a special attention to the case of Ω being the unit ball of \mathbb{R}^3 , see e.g. the survey [Li20].

In this article, we extend the notion of free boundary minimal surface to the nonlocal setting and we study the basic properties of these objects, also discovering some quite surprising facts.

Nonlocal minimal surfaces were first introduced in [CRS10] as minimisers of an integral energy, related to the interfaces of phase transition models accounting for long-range interactions, see e.g. [DV23].

Given an open set $\Omega \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ and a (measurable) set $E \subset \mathbb{R}^n$, we define for $s \in (0, 1)$ the s -fractional perimeter of E in Ω as

$$\text{Per}_s(E; \Omega) := c_{n,s} \left(\int_{E^c \cap \Omega} \int_{E \cap \Omega} + \int_{E \cap \Omega} \int_{E^c \cap \Omega^c} + \int_{E \cap \Omega^c} \int_{E^c \cap \Omega} \right) \frac{dx dy}{|x - y|^{n+s}},$$

where $c_{n,s}$ is a renormalisation constant, given explicitly in formula (1.8) below.

Here above and in the rest of the paper, the notation E^c is used to denote the complementary set of E , namely $E^c := \mathbb{R}^n \setminus E$.

An s -minimal hypersurface in Ω is (the boundary of) a critical point of $\text{Per}_s(\cdot; \Omega)$ with respect to variations compactly supported in Ω . It is well known that critical points satisfy weakly the Euler–Lagrange equation

$$\mathcal{H}_E^s(x) := c_{n,s} \text{p. v.} \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} \frac{\chi_{E^c}(y) - \chi_E(y)}{|x - y|^{n+s}} dy = c_{n,s} \lim_{\delta \rightarrow 0} \int_{\mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_\delta(x)} \frac{\chi_{E^c}(y) - \chi_E(y)}{|x - y|^{n+s}} dy = 0$$

for $x \in \partial E \cap \Omega$, where “p. v.” is a standard abbreviation for wording “in the Cauchy principal value sense”, see e.g. [Fig+15].

Ever since their introduction, these objects have been subject of intensive investigation, concerning both their existence and regularity properties [CV13; SV13; DPW18; CSV19; CCS20], as well as convergence to the classical perimeter [BBM01; Dáv02; CV11; ADM11; Flo24]. Recently, stable and finite-index critical points of the fractional perimeter were studied in the context of closed Riemannian manifolds [Flo24; CFS24a], obtaining, among other things, a nonlocal analogue of Yau’s conjecture in dimension 3 [CFS24b].

Perhaps the most natural question one could ask after defining s -minimal surfaces is a nonlocal analogue of Plateau's problem: given a certain set $E' \subset \Omega^c$, does it exist a set E such that E minimises $\text{Per}_s(\cdot, \Omega)$ among all sets satisfying $E \equiv E'$ in Ω^c ?

This question was already answered positively in the original paper by Caffarelli, Roquejoffre and Savin [CRS10] using the direct method of calculus of variations.

In some sense, Plateau's problem can be interpreted as the Dirichlet problem for the nonlocal minimal surface equation. The goal of the present paper is to introduce the natural Neumann counterpart, namely *free boundary s -minimal hypersurfaces*.

We define free boundary s -minimal hypersurfaces to be boundaries of critical points of $\text{Per}_s(\cdot, \Omega)$ with respect to inner variations compactly supported in \mathbb{R}^n (not necessarily in Ω) and leaving $\partial\Omega$ invariant, namely the variations generated by a vector field which is tangent to $\partial\Omega$ at any of its points.

In particular, we will show that the Euler–Lagrange equations require that critical points satisfy weakly the s -minimal hypersurface equation in Ω

$$c_{n,s} \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} \frac{\chi_{E^c}(y) - \chi_E(y)}{|x-y|^{n+s}} dy = 0, \quad \text{for all } x \in \partial E \cap \Omega \quad (1.1)$$

and the nonlocal free boundary condition outside of Ω

$$c_{n,s} \int_{\Omega} \frac{\chi_{E^c}(y) - \chi_E(y)}{|x-y|^{n+s}} dy = 0, \quad \text{for all } x \in \partial E \cap \bar{\Omega}^c. \quad (1.2)$$

While the quantity in (1.1) is typically referred to as the nonlocal mean curvature (or s -mean curvature) of the set E , the one in (1.2) is a new object accounting for nonlocal interactions of a given point outside Ω with points in the reference set Ω .

Correspondingly, while (1.1) is the Euler–Lagrange equation of the s -perimeter functional with Dirichlet datum, the Neumann counterpart will present equation (1.2) as an additional prescription, with the interesting feature that nonlocal free boundary minimal surfaces satisfy the nonlocal mean curvature equation (1.1) along all boundary points inside the reference set Ω and the “Neumann condition” (1.2) outside the reference set Ω , in a sense that we are now making precise.

1.2. The Euler–Lagrange equation of nonlocal free boundary minimal surfaces.

Let $\Omega \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ be a set with C^1 boundary and consider a vector field $\mathcal{X} \in C_c^\infty(\mathbb{R}^n, \mathbb{R}^n)$ with the property that

$$\mathcal{X}(x) \in T_x(\partial\Omega), \quad \text{for all } x \in \partial\Omega. \quad (1.3)$$

Let Φ_t be the flow associated with \mathcal{X} , namely the solution to $\partial_t \Phi_t = \mathcal{X} \circ \Phi_t$ with initial condition $\Phi_0 = \text{id}$. Given a set E , denote by $E_t := \Phi_t(E)$.

Definition 1.1 (Nonlocal free boundary minimal surfaces). Let $E \subset \mathbb{R}^n$. We say that ∂E is a nonlocal free boundary minimal hypersurface in Ω (or, with a slight abuse of notation, that E is a nonlocal free boundary minimal hypersurface) if, for all $\mathcal{X} \in C_c^\infty(\mathbb{R}^n, \mathbb{R}^n)$ satisfying (1.3),

$$\left. \frac{d}{dt} \right|_{t=0} \text{Per}_s(E_t; \Omega) = 0. \quad (1.4)$$

We will compute (1.4) in a slightly more general setting, where the fractional kernel $c_{n,s}|z|^{-n-s}$ is replaced by a possibly anisotropic kernel.

For this, we say that a kernel $K \in C^1(\mathbb{R}^n \setminus \{0\}, [0, +\infty))$ is an *admissible s-kernel* if it is symmetric around the origin (namely, $K(z) = K(-z)$) and satisfies the bound

$$K(z) \leq \frac{C_K}{|z|^{n+s}} \quad (1.5)$$

for some constant $C_K > 0$.

For $s \in (0, 1)$ and for any admissible s -kernel K , we set

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Per}_K(E; \Omega) &:= \left(\int_{E^c \cap \Omega} \int_{E \cap \Omega} + \int_{E \cap \Omega} \int_{E^c \cap \Omega^c} + \int_{E \cap \Omega^c} \int_{E^c \cap \Omega} \right) K(x-y) dx dy \\ &=: \mathcal{I}_K(E^c \cap \Omega, E \cap \Omega) + \mathcal{I}_K(E \cap \Omega, E^c \cap \Omega^c) + \mathcal{I}_K(E \cap \Omega^c, E^c \cap \Omega). \end{aligned}$$

We also denote, for all $x \in \partial E$,

$$\mathcal{H}_E^K(x) := \text{p. v.} \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} (\chi_{E^c}(y) - \chi_E(y)) K(x-y) dy$$

and, for all $x \in \partial E \cap \bar{\Omega}^c$,

$$\mathcal{A}_{E,\Omega}^K(x) := \int_{\Omega} (\chi_{E^c}(y) - \chi_E(y)) K(x-y) dy.$$

This setting can be considered as a generalization of the nonlocal mean curvature in (1.1) and the free boundary condition in (1.2) to possibly anisotropic kernels.

Given $\alpha \in [0, 1]$, we say that a set $U \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ is of class $C^{1,\alpha}$ if there exist $\rho, M > 0$ such that for every $p \in \partial U$ the set $U \cap B_\rho(p)$ can be written as the subgraph, in some direction, of a function of class $C^{1,\alpha}$ and with $C^{1,\alpha}$ -norm bounded by M .

Furthermore, given $E, \Omega \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ of class C^1 , we say that they intersect uniformly transversally if there exists a constant $\mu \in (0, 1)$ such that

$$\sup_{q \in \partial \Omega \cap \partial E} |\nu_{\partial \Omega}(q) \cdot \nu_{\partial E}(q)| \leq 1 - \mu. \quad (1.6)$$

With this notation, the Euler–Lagrange equation reads as follows.

Theorem 1.2. *Let $s \in (0, 1)$ and K be an admissible s -kernel. Let Ω be a set of class C^1 and E be a set of class $C^{1,\alpha}$ for some $\alpha \in (s, 1)$. Assume also that Ω and E intersect uniformly transversally.*

Let $\mathcal{X} \in C_c^\infty(\mathbb{R}^n, \mathbb{R}^n)$ be a vector field satisfying (1.3) and let Φ_t be the flow generated by \mathcal{X} .

Then,

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d}{dt} \Big|_{t=0} \text{Per}_K(\Phi_t(E); \Omega) \\ = \int_{\partial E \cap \Omega} H_E^K(x) \mathcal{X}(x) \cdot \nu_{\partial E}(x) d\mathcal{H}_x^{n-1} + \int_{\partial E \cap \Omega^c} \mathcal{A}_{E,\Omega}^K(x) \mathcal{X}(x) \cdot \nu_{\partial E}(x) d\mathcal{H}_x^{n-1}. \end{aligned} \quad (1.7)$$

The proof of Theorem 1.2 relies on the strategy developed in [Fig+15, Theorem 6.1], namely one first regularises the kernel and then shows that the result obtained passes to the limit.

To implement the passage to the limit, a pivotal step consists in understanding the asymptotic behaviour of $\mathcal{A}_{E,\Omega}^K$ near $\partial\Omega$. For this, given $\delta > 0$, we consider a δ -tubular neighbourhood T_δ of $\partial\Omega$ defined as

$$T_\delta := \bigcup_{x \in \partial\Omega} B_\delta(x).$$

The result needed for our purposes reads as follows:

Lemma 1.3. *Let $s \in (0, 1)$ and K be an admissible s -kernel. Let Ω be an open set in \mathbb{R}^n of class C^1 .*

Let $\bar{\delta} > 0$ be small enough so that the nearest point projection from $T_{\bar{\delta}}$ to $\partial\Omega$ is well defined.

Then, there exists $\delta_0 \in (0, \bar{\delta})$ such that, for every $\delta \in (0, \delta_0]$ and for every $x \in T_\delta \cap \bar{\Omega}^c$,

$$\int_{\Omega} K(x-y)dy \leq C \operatorname{dist}(x, \Omega)^{-s}$$

for some $C > 0$ depending only on C_K , n and s .

We will prove Theorem 1.2 and Lemma 1.3 in Section 2 below.

Example 1.4. The simplest nontrivial example of a free boundary s -minimal surface is the hyperplane $\partial\{y_n < 0\}$ in the unit ball. The interior equation (1.1) is satisfied in every compact set, while the free boundary condition (1.2) holds by symmetry.

1.3. The free boundary condition in the limit as $s \nearrow 1$. As a natural next step, we show that the nonlocal free boundary condition “converges”, in some suitable sense, to the local one, as $s \nearrow 1$.

For this, let us recall that the constant $c_{n,s}$ is explicitly given by

$$c_{n,s} := \frac{2^{2+2s}\Gamma\left(\frac{n+s}{2}\right)}{\pi^{n/2}\Gamma(2-s)}s(1-s) \tag{1.8}$$

and we have the limits

$$\lim_{s \searrow 0} \frac{c_{n,s}}{s} = \frac{8}{\omega_n} \quad \text{and} \quad \lim_{s \nearrow 1} \frac{c_{n,s}}{1-s} = \frac{16n}{\omega_n}, \tag{1.9}$$

see, for instance, [ADV25, §1.6.2]. Here above ω_n denotes the surface measure of the $(n-1)$ -dimensional sphere $\partial B_1 \subset \mathbb{R}^n$.

We show that the free boundary condition (1.2), defined on $\partial E \cap \Omega^c$, concentrates on $\partial E \cap \partial\Omega$ as $s \nearrow 1$, according to the following statement:

Theorem 1.5. *Let E and Ω be open sets of class $C^{1,1}$ intersecting uniformly transversally. Let $\mathcal{X} \in C_c^\infty(\mathbb{R}^n, \mathbb{R}^n)$ be a vector field satisfying (1.3).*

Then,

$$\lim_{s \nearrow 1} \int_{\partial E \cap \Omega^c} \mathcal{A}_{E,\Omega}^s(x) \mathcal{X}(x) \cdot \nu_{\partial E}(x) d\mathcal{H}_x^{n-1} = \int_{\partial E \cap \partial \Omega} g(\psi_{x'}) \mathcal{X}(x') \cdot \nu_{\partial E}(x') d\mathcal{H}_{x'}^{n-2},$$

where

$$g(\psi) := \int_{\{Z_n \in ((Z_1-1)/\tan \psi, (1-Z_1)/\tan \psi)\}^{\{Z_1 < 0\}}} \frac{dZ}{|Z - e_1|^{n+1}}$$

and $\psi_{x'}$ is the intersection angle between the affine hyperplanes $T_{x'}(\partial E)$ and $T_{x'}(\partial \Omega)$.

An immediate consequence of Theorem 1.5 is the following.

Corollary 1.6. *Under the same assumptions of Theorem 1.5,*

$$\lim_{s \nearrow 1} \int_{\partial E \cap \Omega^c} \mathcal{A}_{E,\Omega}^s(x) \mathcal{X}(x) \cdot \nu_{\partial E}(x) d\mathcal{H}_x^{n-1} = 0$$

if and only if ∂E meets $\partial \Omega$ orthogonally in the support of \mathcal{X} .

We refer to Section 3 below for the proof of Theorem 1.5.

1.4. A free boundary s -minimal surface *without* free boundary. In the classical case, if the reference domain Ω is bounded, the boundary of a smooth free boundary minimal surface E must always meet the boundary of Ω (unless E is either void or contains the whole domain). Indeed, otherwise, assuming that $0 \in \Omega$, one could pick a point $p \in \partial E$ that maximises the distance from the origin and note that either $E \subseteq B_r$ or $E^c \subseteq B_r$, with $r := |p|$. The mean curvature of ∂E at p would then be bounded below by $\frac{1}{r}$ (when $E \subseteq B_r$) or above by $-\frac{1}{r}$ (when $E^c \subseteq B_r$), thus contradicting the zero mean curvature condition.

Alternatively, one can observe that there are no closed minimal hypersurfaces Σ in \mathbb{R}^n , since the coordinate functions $x_1, \dots, x_n: \Sigma \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ are harmonic on Σ and therefore constant if Σ has no boundary. This entails that a free boundary minimal hypersurface in a compact manifold Ω always meets the boundary.

In stark contrast with the local case, we show that, in the asymptotic regime $s \sim 0$, there exist free boundary s -minimal hypersurfaces without any boundary contact set. Moreover, such surfaces are radially symmetric, which is again an exclusively nonlocal feature. The precise statement is the following:

Theorem 1.7. *There exists $s_o \in (0, 1)$ such that for every $s \in (0, s_o)$ there exist radii $0 < r_1 < 1 < r_2$ such that $\partial(B_{r_2} \setminus B_{r_1})$ is a free boundary s -minimal hypersurface in B_1 .*

Theorem 1.7 will be established in Section 4.

1.5. The volume condition for unbounded sets. We also prove a remarkably simple and powerful property of free boundary s -minimal hypersurfaces: whenever ∂E is unbounded and Ω is bounded, the volume of E in Ω must coincide with the volume of E^c in Ω .

Theorem 1.8. *Let $s \in (0, 1)$, Ω be an open, bounded set and E be a free boundary s -minimal surface with ∂E unbounded.*

Then,

$$\mathcal{H}^n(E \cap \Omega) = \mathcal{H}^n(E^c \cap \Omega). \quad (1.10)$$

The proof of Theorem 1.8 is contained in Section 5.

Remark 1.9. The assumption of ∂E being unbounded in Theorem 1.8 is necessary, as can be seen from the example of Theorem 1.7.

The volume condition (1.10) can be used to show that many natural candidates for the nonlocal analogues of classical free boundary minimal surfaces are not actually free boundary s -minimal surfaces for most (if not any) $s \in (0, 1)$.

Consider the Lawson cones in \mathbb{R}^{n+m}

$$C^{n,m}(\alpha) := \{(x, y) \in \mathbb{R}^n \times \mathbb{R}^m : |x| < \alpha|y|\}.$$

It was proved in [DPW18] that for every $n, m \geq 1$ and every $s \in (0, 1)$ there exists a unique $\alpha = \alpha(s, n, m) > 0$ such that $\partial C^{n,m}(\alpha)$ is a critical point for the s -perimeter. For such α , we denote the solid cone by $C_s^{n,m}$. We remark that, by symmetry, for any $n \geq 1$ and every $s \in (0, 1)$,

$$\alpha(s, n, n) = 1. \quad (1.11)$$

In [DPW18] it was also proved that

$$\alpha(s, 2, 1) = \sqrt{1-s} + O(1-s) \quad \text{as } s \nearrow 1, \quad (1.12)$$

thus, the opening of the s -critical Lawson cone in \mathbb{R}^3 vanishes as $s \nearrow 1$. Such cone arises as the blow-down of the fractional catenoid F_s , constructed in [DPW18]. We recall that, as $s \nearrow 1$, F_s converges to the set F_* whose boundary is a classical catenoid, uniformly in every compact set.

It is reasonable to wonder whether s -critical Lawson cones are free boundary s -minimal hypersurfaces in any ball, since any of these cones trivially satisfies the classical free boundary condition.

Moreover, a simple limiting argument shows the existence of a ball in which the catenoid is a free boundary minimal surface, thus it is natural to wonder whether the fractional analogues F_s are free boundary in some ball.

The volume condition (1.10) entails that this is not the case, according to the following result.

Corollary 1.10. *There exists $\bar{s} \in (0, 1)$ such that for all $s \in (\bar{s}, 1)$ the Lawson cone $C_s^{2,1}$ and the fractional catenoids F_s are not free boundary s -minimal surfaces in any ball $B_R(0) \subset \mathbb{R}^3$.*

Remark 1.11. By the monotonicity and the continuity of the map

$$\alpha \rightarrow \mathcal{H}^{n+m}(C^{n,m}(\alpha) \cap B_1),$$

along with the facts that

$$\mathcal{H}^{n+m}(C^{n,m}(0) \cap B_1) = 0 \quad \text{and} \quad \mathcal{H}^{n+m}(C^{n,m}(\infty) \cap B_1) = \mathcal{H}^{n+m}(B_1),$$

FIGURE 1. Different types of stickiness: from inside on x_1 , from outside on x_2 and bilateral on x_3 .

we infer the existence of a unique α such that

$$\mathcal{H}^{n+m}(C^{n,m}(\alpha) \cap B_1) = \frac{\mathcal{H}^{n+m}(B_1)}{2}. \quad (1.13)$$

Notice that (1.13) corresponds to the volume condition in (1.10) in this setting.

In the case $n = m$, by symmetry, we also know that $C^{n,n}(1)$ is a free boundary s -minimal surface in any ball. Therefore, in this setting, the unique α satisfying (1.13) is $\alpha = 1$, and all the other cones $C^{n,n}(\alpha)$, with $\alpha \neq 1$, are not free boundary s -minimal surfaces in B_1 .

It would be interesting to classify all the fractional Lawson cones $C_s^{m,n}$ which are free boundary s -minimal surfaces also when $n \neq m$. The fact that the volume condition (1.10) does not depend on s suggests that it is “difficult” for $C_s^{m,n}$ to satisfy this condition for a “generic” s and one may even conjecture that the only fractional Lawson cones that are free boundary in a ball are the symmetric cones $C^{n,n}(1)$.

1.6. Stickiness and regularity across the boundary. The “stickiness” phenomenon was introduced in [DSV17] and describes the (generic, see [DSV20]) tendency of minimisers of the fractional perimeter to share a portion of boundary with the ambient domain Ω , effectively “sticking” to it.

In this paper, we investigate stickiness properties of free boundary s -minimal surfaces, see Section 6 below. For this purpose, we give the following definitions:

Definition 1.12 (Stickiness). Let E and Ω be open sets of \mathbb{R}^n of class C^0 and let $x \in \partial E \cap \partial \Omega$. We say that the set E sticks to Ω at x if there exists $\rho > 0$ such that

$$\begin{aligned} &\text{either } \Omega \cap B_\rho(x) \subset E \text{ and } \Omega^c \cap B_\rho(x) \subset E^c \\ &\text{or } \Omega \cap B_\rho(x) \subset E^c \text{ and } \Omega^c \cap B_\rho(x) \subset E. \end{aligned}$$

Definition 1.13 (Stickiness from outside). Let E and Ω be open sets of \mathbb{R}^n of class C^0 and let $x \in \partial E \cap \partial\Omega$. We say that the set E sticks to Ω from outside at x if there exists $\rho > 0$ such that

$$\begin{aligned} & \text{either } \Omega \cap B_\rho(x) \subset E \text{ and } \Omega^c \cap B_\rho(x) \cap E \neq \emptyset \\ & \text{or } \Omega \cap B_\rho(x) \subset E^c \text{ and } \Omega^c \cap B_\rho(x) \cap E^c \neq \emptyset. \end{aligned}$$

Definition 1.14 (Stickiness from inside). Let E and Ω be open sets of \mathbb{R}^n of class C^0 and let $x \in \partial E \cap \partial\Omega$. We say that the set E sticks to Ω from inside at x if there exists $\rho > 0$ such that

$$\begin{aligned} & \text{either } \Omega^c \cap B_\rho(x) \subset E^c \text{ and } \Omega \cap B_\rho(x) \cap E^c \neq \emptyset \\ & \text{or } \Omega^c \cap B_\rho(x) \subset E \text{ and } \Omega \cap B_\rho(x) \cap E \neq \emptyset. \end{aligned}$$

See Figure 1 for a depiction of the different types of stickiness.

In the context of free boundary s -minimal hypersurfaces, stickiness is quite subtle. Indeed, the behaviour that it describes is exactly the opposite of what one expects from the local counterpart, where the hypersurface meets the boundary orthogonally.

On the other hand, at the level of the first variation (1.7), in any portion of ∂E sticking to $\partial\Omega$ the term $\mathcal{X} \cdot \nu_{\partial E}$ vanishes, as a consequence of (1.3). This brings us to the following simple but instructive example.

Example 1.15 (Total stickiness). The set Ω itself, and its complement, are free boundary s -minimal surfaces in Ω for any $s \in (0, 1)$.

Indeed, by the tangency condition (1.3), the flow leaves Ω unchanged, and therefore $\text{Per}_s(\Omega; \Omega)$ is constant for inner variations preserving $\partial\Omega$.

We point out that Example 1.15 is a degenerate situation, which is the nonlocal analogue of the fact that (if one allows it) $\partial\Omega$ is a classical free boundary minimal hypersurface in Ω , since it is unchanged by flows tangent to $\partial\Omega$.

Next, we show that there are non-trivial examples of stickiness for critical points.

Example 1.16. Let $\Omega := B_1 \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ and

$$E := \{x \in B_1 : x_n > 0\} \cup \{x \in B_1^c : x_n < 0\}.$$

Then, E is a free boundary s -minimal surface in Ω for every $s \in (0, 1)$, with

$$\Lambda := \{x \in \partial E \cap \partial\Omega : E \text{ sticks to } \Omega \text{ at } x\} \neq \emptyset$$

(in fact, with Λ dense in $\partial\Omega$, being the unit sphere minus the equator). Indeed, in all points of $\partial E \cap \Omega$ and $\partial E \cap \Omega^c$ the equations (1.1) and (1.2) are strongly satisfied by symmetry.

Using the same strategy we can construct many other examples. For any integer $k \geq 1$ consider the set

$$\tilde{E} := \left\{ r e^{i\theta} \in \mathbb{C} \simeq \mathbb{R}^2 : r > 0, \theta \in \left(\frac{\pi}{k}(2j), \frac{\pi}{k}(2j+1) \right), j = 0, \dots, k-1 \right\}$$

given by cone in \mathbb{R}^2 over every other arc in \mathbb{S}^1 connecting $2k$ equi-spaced points.

FIGURE 2. The set E (in grey) is a free boundary s -minimal surface, with stickiness, in the unit circle (in light blue).

One can check easily, still by symmetry, that $\partial\tilde{E}$ is a (non sticking) free boundary minimal hypersurface in B_1 .

On the other hand, the set

$$E := (\tilde{E} \cap B_1) \cup (\tilde{E}^c \cap B_1^c)$$

is a free boundary s -minimal hypersurface in B_1 , sticking on the whole unit circle minus the $2k$ points, see Figure 2.

The sets constructed in Example 1.16 show that stickiness can happen for free boundary s -minimal hypersurfaces. Our next result establishes that the same is not true if we consider only stickiness from outside.

Theorem 1.17. *Let $s \in (0, 1)$ and E be a free boundary s -minimal surface in Ω of class C^0 . Then, there are no points on $\partial E \cap \partial\Omega$ at which E sticks to Ω from outside.*

We remark that there is no counterpart of Theorem 1.17 in the setting of sticking from inside. Indeed, sticking from inside can happen in general. A simple example is given by

$$E := \{(y', y_n) \in \mathbb{R}^n : y_n > 0\}$$

and $\Omega := \{(y', y_n) \in \mathbb{R}^n : y_n > \varphi(y')\},$

where φ is a smooth function such that $\varphi \equiv 0$ in B_1 and $\varphi < 0$ in B_1^c .

This kind of “lack of symmetry” for the two types of stickiness, from outside and from inside, is due to the fact the equations in (1.1) and (1.2) are fundamentally different. Indeed, the proof of Theorem 1.17 exploits a limiting process for the free boundary equation that allows us to reach a contradiction, while a similar limiting process for the mean curvature equation would be inconclusive since there could be a compensation between the contributions from inside and outside of Ω .

It would be interesting to investigate the phenomenon of sticking from inside in cases in which Ω is convex, mean-convex or even just bounded.

Nevertheless we are able to show that, if ∂E crosses $\partial\Omega$ without sticking and it is regular enough away from $\partial\Omega$, then the intersection is orthogonal and the set is regular across $\partial\Omega$.

Theorem 1.18. *Let $s \in (0, 1)$ and $\alpha \in (s, 1]$. Let Ω be an open set of \mathbb{R}^n of class $C^{1,\alpha}$. Let E be a free boundary s -minimal surface in Ω .*

Assume that $0 \in \partial E \cap \partial\Omega$ and that there exist $r > 0$ and a diffeomorphism $T : \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^n$ of class $C^{1,\alpha}$, with $T(0) = 0$, $DT(0) = \text{Id}$, $T(B_r) = B_r$, $T(B_r \cap \Omega) = B_r \cap \{x_1 > 0\}$ and $T(E \cap B_r) = E_1 \cup E_2$, where

$$\begin{aligned} E_1 &:= \{x \in B_r \text{ s.t. } x_1 \geq 0 \text{ and } \omega_1 \cdot x < 0\} \\ \text{and } E_2 &:= \{x \in B_r \text{ s.t. } x_1 \leq 0 \text{ and } \omega_2 \cdot x < 0\}, \end{aligned} \tag{1.14}$$

for some unit vectors $\omega_1, \omega_2 \in \mathbb{R}^n$ of the form

$$\omega_1 = (-\sin \vartheta_1, 0 \dots, 0, \cos \vartheta_1) \quad \text{and} \quad \omega_2 = (-\sin \vartheta_2, 0 \dots, 0, \cos \vartheta_2).$$

Assume also that

$$\vartheta_1, \vartheta_2 \in \left(-\frac{\pi}{2}, \frac{\pi}{2}\right). \tag{1.15}$$

Then $\vartheta_1 = \vartheta_2 = 0$, and in particular E is of class $C^{1,\alpha}$ in the vicinity of the origin and the intersection of ∂E and $\partial\Omega$ at the origin is orthogonal.

We stress that condition (1.15) is related to the fact that ∂E and $\partial\Omega$ do not adhere to each other at the origin (which is supposed to be a common boundary point). Moreover, condition (1.14) says, in a nutshell, that E is of class $C^{1,\alpha}$ near the origin “from both sides” of $\partial\Omega$. In this spirit, Theorem 1.18 guarantees that E is, in fact, $C^{1,\alpha}$ through the origin as well.

Natural questions regarding the nonlocal free boundary minimal surfaces involve their regularity and density properties. For instance one may wonder whether they are always smooth, whether a point on their boundary presents uniform densities of the set and its complement, and whether, in a given ball, it always presents two balls of comparable radii contained, respectively, in the set and its complement (this is the so-called “clean ball condition”). Interestingly, all these properties do *not* hold true in our setting. As a counterexample, one can consider, for all $N \in \mathbb{N} \cap [2, +\infty)$, the planar set defined in complex notation by

$$E_N := \left\{ r e^{i\vartheta}, \text{ with } r > 0 \text{ and } \vartheta \in \bigcup_{j=0}^{N-1} \left(\frac{2j\pi}{N}, \frac{(2j+1)\pi}{N} \right) \right\}.$$

By symmetry, E_N is a nonlocal free boundary minimal surface in any ball centered at the origin, but, at the origin, it violates smoothness, and does not satisfy density estimates and clean ball conditions with respect to uniform quantities (any property of this type actually degenerates when N gets larger and larger).

We now dive into the technical part of this paper, by providing the proofs of the main results.

2. THE EULER–LAGRANGE EQUATIONS AND PROOF OF THEOREM 1.2

In this section we prove Theorem 1.2. We will follow the strategy of [Fig+15, Theorem 6.1], by first regularising the kernel and then showing that the result passes to the limit. We begin by proving Lemma 1.3.

Proof of Lemma 1.3. For every $x \in T_{\bar{\delta}}$, we denote by $\pi_x \in \partial\Omega$ the nearest point projection of x and let $d_x := \text{dist}(x, \Omega) = |x - \pi_x|$.

Now let $x \in T_{\bar{\delta}} \cap \bar{\Omega}^c$ and let $P_x: \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^n$ be a rigid motion that maps π_x to 0 and x to $d_x e_n$. Then, recalling (1.5), and using the changes of variables $z := P_x y$ and $w := z/d_x$, we find that

$$\begin{aligned} \int_{\Omega} K(x-y) dy &\leq C_K \int_{\Omega} \frac{dy}{|x-y|^{n+s}} \\ &= C_K \int_{P_x \Omega} \frac{dz}{|d_x e_n - z|^{n+s}} = \frac{C_K}{d_x^s} \int_{d_x^{-1} P_x \Omega} \frac{dw}{|e_n - w|^{n+s}}. \end{aligned} \quad (2.1)$$

We point out that $d_x^{-1} P_x \Omega$ converges to $\{y_n < 0\}$ as $d_x \rightarrow 0$, namely as $x \rightarrow \partial\Omega$. As a result, there exists $\delta_0 \in (0, \bar{\delta})$ such that, for all $x \in T_{\delta_0} \cap \bar{\Omega}^c$,

$$\int_{d_x^{-1} P_x \Omega} \frac{dw}{|e_n - w|^{n+s}} \leq 1 + \int_{\{w_n < 0\}} \frac{dw}{|e_n - w|^{n+s}} < +\infty.$$

Plugging this information into (2.1), we conclude that, for all $x \in T_{\delta_0} \cap \bar{\Omega}^c$,

$$\int_{\Omega} K(x-y) dy \leq \frac{C C_K}{d_x^s},$$

for some $C > 0$ depending only on n and s . This entails the desired result. \square

Proof of Theorem 1.2. Given $\delta > 0$ sufficiently small, consider a smooth, monotone family of cut-off functions $\eta_{\delta}: [0, +\infty) \rightarrow [0, 1]$ such that

$$\eta_{\delta} \equiv 1 \text{ in } [0, \delta] \cup \left[\frac{1}{\delta}, +\infty\right), \quad \eta_{\delta} \equiv 0 \text{ in } \left[2\delta, \frac{1}{2\delta}\right] \quad \text{and} \quad |\eta'_{\delta}| \leq \frac{2}{\delta}.$$

We define the regularised kernel $K_{\delta}(z) := (1 - \eta_{\delta}(|z|))K(z)$.

Note that, as a consequence of the tangency condition (1.3), the flow leaves Ω unchanged, namely

$$\Phi_t(\Omega) = \Omega \quad (\text{and clearly } \Phi_t(\Omega^c) = \Omega^c).$$

Moreover, we have that

$$\frac{d}{dt} \text{Per}_{K_{\delta}}(E_t; \Omega) = \frac{d}{dh} \Big|_{h=0} \text{Per}_{K_{\delta}}(E_{t+h}; \Omega),$$

see page 481 in [Fig+15].

Using these facts, we compute, for $|t|$ and $|h|$ small,

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{I}_{K_\delta}(E_{t+h}^c \cap \Omega, E_{t+h} \cap \Omega) &= \int_{E_{t+h}^c \cap \Omega} \int_{E_{t+h} \cap \Omega} K_\delta(x-y) dx dy \\ &= \int_{E_t^c \cap \Omega} \int_{E_t \cap \Omega} K_\delta(\Phi_h(x) - \Phi_h(y)) J_{\Phi_h}(x) J_{\Phi_h}(y) dx dy. \end{aligned}$$

where J_{Φ_h} is the Jacobian determinant of the change of variable Φ_h , which can be expanded as $J_{\Phi_h} = \text{id} + h\mathcal{X} + O(h^2)$.

Thus, we can write

$$\frac{d}{dt} \mathcal{I}_{K_\delta}(E_t^c \cap \Omega, E_t \cap \Omega) = A_1 + A_2,$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} A_1 &:= \int_{E_t^c \cap \Omega} \int_{E_t \cap \Omega} \nabla K_\delta(x-y) (\mathcal{X}(x) - \mathcal{X}(y)) dx dy \\ \text{and } A_2 &:= \int_{E_t^c \cap \Omega} \int_{E_t \cap \Omega} K_\delta(x-y) (\text{div } \mathcal{X}(x) + \text{div } \mathcal{X}(y)) dx dy. \end{aligned}$$

By the symmetry of K and integrating by parts in A_1 , we get

$$\begin{aligned} A_1 &= \int_{E_t^c \cap \Omega} \left(\int_{E_t \cap \Omega} \nabla K_\delta(x-y) \cdot \mathcal{X}(x) dx \right) dy + \int_{E_t \cap \Omega} \left(\int_{E_t^c \cap \Omega} \nabla K_\delta(y-x) \cdot \mathcal{X}(y) dy \right) dx \\ &= - \int_{E_t^c \cap \Omega} \int_{E_t \cap \Omega} K_\delta(x-y) \text{div } \mathcal{X}(x) dx dy \\ &\quad + \int_{E_t^c \cap \Omega} \int_{\partial(E_t \cap \Omega)} K_\delta(x-y) \mathcal{X}(x) \cdot \nu_{\partial(E_t \cap \Omega)}(x) d\mathcal{H}_x^{n-1} dy \\ &\quad - \int_{E_t \cap \Omega} \int_{E_t^c \cap \Omega} K_\delta(x-y) \text{div } \mathcal{X}(y) dx dy \\ &\quad + \int_{E_t \cap \Omega} \int_{\partial(E_t^c \cap \Omega)} K_\delta(x-y) \mathcal{X}(y) \cdot \nu_{\partial(E_t^c \cap \Omega)}(y) d\mathcal{H}_y^{n-1} dx. \end{aligned}$$

We observe that the sum of the first and the third terms in the last expression equals $-A_2$, and therefore

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d}{dt} \mathcal{I}_{K_\delta}(E_t^c \cap \Omega, E_t \cap \Omega) &= \int_{E_t^c \cap \Omega} \int_{\partial(E_t \cap \Omega)} K_\delta(x-y) \mathcal{X}(x) \cdot \nu_{\partial(E_t \cap \Omega)}(x) d\mathcal{H}_x^{n-1} dy \\ &\quad + \int_{E_t \cap \Omega} \int_{\partial(E_t^c \cap \Omega)} K_\delta(x-y) \mathcal{X}(y) \cdot \nu_{\partial(E_t^c \cap \Omega)}(y) d\mathcal{H}_y^{n-1} dx. \end{aligned} \tag{2.2}$$

We also remark that $\partial(E_t \cap \Omega) = (\partial E_t \cap \Omega) \cup (E_t \cap \partial \Omega)$ and, for $x \in E_t \cap \partial \Omega$,

$$\nu_{\partial(E_t \cap \Omega)}(x) = \nu_{\partial \Omega}(x).$$

Hence, by the tangency condition (1.3), we deduce that

$$\mathcal{X}(x) \cdot \nu_{\partial(E_t \cap \Omega)}(x) = 0 \quad \text{for all } x \in E_t \cap \partial\Omega.$$

Moreover,

$$\partial(E_t^c \cap \Omega) = (\partial E_t^c \cap \Omega) \cup (E_t^c \cap \partial\Omega) = (\partial E_t \cap \Omega) \cup (E_t^c \cap \partial\Omega)$$

and we have that

$$\mathcal{X}(y) \cdot \nu_{\partial(E_t^c \cap \Omega)}(y) = 0 \quad \text{for all } y \in E_t^c \cap \partial\Omega$$

$$\text{and} \quad \mathcal{X}(y) \cdot \nu_{\partial(E_t^c \cap \Omega)}(y) = -\mathcal{X}(y) \cdot \nu_{\partial(E_t \cap \Omega)}(y) \quad \text{for all } y \in \partial E_t^c \cap \Omega.$$

As a result, using these pieces of information into (2.2), we conclude that

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{d}{dt} \mathcal{I}_{K_\delta}(E_t^c \cap \Omega, E_t \cap \Omega) \\ &= \int_{E_t^c \cap \Omega} \int_{\partial E_t \cap \Omega} K_\delta(x-y) \mathcal{X}(x) \cdot \nu_{\partial E_t}(x) d\mathcal{H}_x^{n-1} dy \\ & \quad - \int_{E_t \cap \Omega} \int_{\partial E_t \cap \Omega} K_\delta(x-y) \mathcal{X}(y) \cdot \nu_{\partial E_t}(y) d\mathcal{H}_y^{n-1} dx. \end{aligned}$$

Similar computations lead to

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{d}{dt} \mathcal{I}_{K_\delta}(E_t \cap \Omega, E_t^c \cap \Omega^c) \\ &= \int_{E_t^c \cap \Omega^c} \int_{\partial E_t \cap \Omega} K_\delta(x-y) \mathcal{X}(x) \cdot \nu_{\partial E_t}(x) d\mathcal{H}_x^{n-1} dy \\ & \quad - \int_{E_t \cap \Omega} \int_{\partial E_t \cap \Omega^c} K_\delta(x-y) \mathcal{X}(y) \cdot \nu_{\partial E_t}(y) d\mathcal{H}_y^{n-1} dx \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{d}{dt} \mathcal{I}_{K_\delta}(E_t \cap \Omega^c, E_t^c \cap \Omega) \\ &= \int_{E_t^c \cap \Omega} \int_{\partial E_t \cap \Omega^c} K_\delta(x-y) \mathcal{X}(x) \cdot \nu_{\partial E_t}(x) d\mathcal{H}_x^{n-1} dy \\ & \quad - \int_{E_t \cap \Omega^c} \int_{\partial E_t \cap \Omega} K_\delta(x-y) \mathcal{X}(y) \cdot \nu_{\partial E_t}(y) d\mathcal{H}_y^{n-1} dx. \end{aligned}$$

Thus, putting everything together, we find that, for $|t|$ small,

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{d}{dt} \text{Per}_{K_\delta}(E_t; \Omega) \\ &= \int_{\partial E_t \cap \Omega} \left(\int_{E_t^c} K_\delta(x-y) dy - \int_{E_t} K_\delta(x-y) dy \right) \mathcal{X}(x) \cdot \nu_{\partial E_t}(x) d\mathcal{H}_x^{n-1} \\ & \quad + \int_{\partial E_t \cap \Omega^c} \left(\int_{E_t^c \cap \Omega} K_\delta(x-y) dy - \int_{E_t \cap \Omega} K_\delta(x-y) dy \right) \mathcal{X}(x) \cdot \nu_{\partial E_t}(x) d\mathcal{H}_x^{n-1}. \end{aligned} \tag{2.3}$$

Next, we consider the limit as $\delta \searrow 0^+$. For this, we set

$$\phi_\delta(t) := \text{Per}_{K_\delta}(E_t; \Omega) \quad \text{and} \quad \phi(t) := \text{Per}_K(E_t; \Omega).$$

Our goal is to show that

$$\phi'(0) = \int_{\partial E \cap \Omega} \mathcal{H}_E^K(x) \xi(x) d\mathcal{H}_x^{n-1} + \int_{\partial E \cap \Omega^c} \mathcal{A}_{E, \Omega}^K(x) \xi(x) d\mathcal{H}_x^{n-1} \quad (2.4)$$

where $\xi(x) := \mathcal{X}(x) \cdot \nu_{\partial E}(x)$.

To this aim, we notice that, by the Monotone Convergence Theorem, for $|t|$ small, say $|t| < \varepsilon$,

$$\lim_{\delta \searrow 0} \phi_\delta(t) = \phi(t). \quad (2.5)$$

Moreover, by (2.3),

$$\phi'_\delta(t) = \int_{\partial E_t \cap \Omega} \mathcal{H}_{E_t}^{K_\delta}(x) \xi(x) d\mathcal{H}_x^{n-1} + \int_{\partial E_t \cap \Omega^c} \mathcal{A}_{E_t, \Omega}^{K_\delta}(x) \xi(x) d\mathcal{H}_x^{n-1}. \quad (2.6)$$

Next, we perform a passage to the limit as $\delta \searrow 0$ of the derivative by showing uniform convergence to the desired quantity. In this step, the argument to show convergence of $\mathcal{H}_{E_t}^{K_\delta}$ and $\mathcal{A}_{E_t, \Omega}^{K_\delta}$ is very different. Indeed, by [Fig+15, Proposition 6.3] the approximated curvatures $\mathcal{H}_{E_t}^{K_\delta}$ are uniformly close to $\mathcal{H}_{E_t}^K$ in the whole region $\partial E_t \cap \Omega$. Note that the proof of [Fig+15, Proposition 6.3] provides estimates in Ω which are robust as long as E is $C^{1, \alpha}$ in Ω , with $\alpha \in (s, 1)$. In particular, we have that

$$\lim_{\delta \rightarrow 0^+} \sup_{|t| < \varepsilon} \sup_{\partial E_t \cap \Omega \cap \text{spt } \xi} |\mathcal{H}_{E_t}^K - \mathcal{H}_{E_t}^{K_\delta}| = 0, \quad (2.7)$$

see [Fig+15, formula (6.24)].

The same argument cannot be made for $\mathcal{A}_{E_t, \Omega}^{K_\delta}$, since it would imply uniform convergence of the bounded quantities $\mathcal{A}_{E_t, \Omega}^{K_\delta}$ to the unbounded quantity $\mathcal{A}_{E_t, \Omega}^K$ in $\partial E \cap \Omega^c$. Instead, we proceed as follows: let δ_0 be given by Lemma 1.3 and let $\delta \in (0, \frac{\delta_0}{2})$. Let $T_{2\delta}$ be a 2δ -tubular neighbourhood of $\partial\Omega$. Note that, for all $x \in \partial E_t \cap \overline{\Omega}^c \cap T_{2\delta}^c$,

$$\begin{aligned} |\mathcal{A}_{E_t, \Omega}^{K_\delta}(x) - \mathcal{A}_{E_t, \Omega}^K(x)| &= \left| \int_{\Omega} (\chi_{E_t^c}(y) - \chi_{E_t}(y)) \eta_\delta(|x-y|) K(x-y) dy \right| \\ &\leq 2 \int_{B_{1/2\delta}^c} K(z) dz \leq 2C_K \int_{B_{1/2\delta}^c} \frac{dz}{|z|^{n+s}} = \frac{2^{1+s} C_K \omega_n}{s} \delta^s. \end{aligned}$$

As a consequence, since ξ is compactly supported,

$$\left| \int_{\partial E_t \cap \Omega^c \cap T_{2\delta}^c} (\mathcal{A}_{E_t, \Omega}^{K_\delta}(x) - \mathcal{A}_{E_t, \Omega}^K(x)) \xi(x) d\mathcal{H}_x^{n-1} \right| \leq C \|\mathcal{X}\|_{L^\infty(\mathbb{R}^n, \mathbb{R}^n)} \delta^s, \quad (2.8)$$

up to renaming C .

Furthermore, if $x \in \partial E_t \cap \overline{\Omega}^c \cap T_{2\delta}$, thanks to Lemma 1.3 we have that

$$\begin{aligned} |\mathcal{A}_{E_t, \Omega}^{K_\delta}(x) - \mathcal{A}_{E_t, \Omega}^K(x)| &= \left| \int_{\Omega} (\chi_{E_t^c}(y) - \chi_{E_t}(y)) \eta_\delta(|x-y|) K(x-y) dy \right| \\ &\leq \int_{\Omega} K(x-y) dy \leq C \operatorname{dist}(x, \Omega)^{-s}, \end{aligned}$$

where $C > 0$ depends on C_K , n and s .

Therefore,

$$\begin{aligned} &\left| \int_{\partial E_t \cap \Omega^c \cap T_{2\delta}} \left(\mathcal{A}_{E_t, \Omega}^{K_\delta}(x) - \mathcal{A}_{E_t, \Omega}^K(x) \right) \xi(x) d\mathcal{H}_x^{n-1} \right| \\ &\leq C \int_{\partial E_t \cap \Omega^c \cap T_{2\delta}} \operatorname{dist}(x, \Omega)^{-s} |\xi(x)| d\mathcal{H}_x^{n-1}. \end{aligned} \quad (2.9)$$

Now, we suppose that the support of \mathcal{X} is contained in some ball B_R , and we use the regularity assumption on ∂E to conclude that there exist $\rho > 0$, $N \in \mathbb{N}$ and $p_1, \dots, p_N \in \mathbb{R}^n$ such that, for t sufficiently small,

$$\partial E_t \cap B_R \subset \bigcup_{i=1}^N B_\rho(p_i)$$

and $\partial E_t \cap B_\rho(p_i)$ is the graph of a $C^{1,\alpha}$ -function.

Using this information into (2.9), we find that

$$\begin{aligned} &\left| \int_{\partial E_t \cap \Omega^c \cap T_{2\delta}} \left(\mathcal{A}_{E_t, \Omega}^{K_\delta}(x) - \mathcal{A}_{E_t, \Omega}^K(x) \right) \xi(x) d\mathcal{H}_x^{n-1} \right| \\ &\leq C \int_{\partial E_t \cap \Omega^c \cap T_{2\delta} \cap B_R} \operatorname{dist}(x, \Omega)^{-s} |\xi(x)| d\mathcal{H}_x^{n-1} \\ &\leq C \sum_{i=1}^N \int_{\partial E_t \cap \Omega^c \cap T_{2\delta} \cap B_\rho(p_i)} \operatorname{dist}(x, \Omega)^{-s} |\xi(x)| d\mathcal{H}_x^{n-1} \\ &\leq C \|\mathcal{X}\|_{L^\infty(\mathbb{R}^n, \mathbb{R}^n)} \sum_{i=1}^N \int_{\partial E_t \cap \Omega^c \cap T_{2\delta} \cap B_\rho(p_i)} \operatorname{dist}(x, \Omega)^{-s} d\mathcal{H}_x^{n-1}. \end{aligned} \quad (2.10)$$

Now we let $\pi_x \in \partial\Omega$ be such that $|x - \pi_x| = \operatorname{dist}(x, \Omega)$ and consider a diffeomorphism of $B_\rho(p_i)$ of class C^1 which places ∂E_t into $\Sigma := \{x_n = 0\}$ and Ω into $L := \{\cos \theta x_n < \sin \theta x_{n-1}\}$ for some $\theta \in (0, \frac{\pi}{2}]$ (we stress that we are using here the transversality assumption between E_t and Ω).

In this way,

$$\begin{aligned} &\int_{\partial E_t \cap \Omega^c \cap T_{2\delta} \cap B_\rho(p_i)} \operatorname{dist}(x, \Omega)^{-s} d\mathcal{H}_x^{n-1} = \int_{\partial E_t \cap \Omega^c \cap T_{2\delta} \cap B_\rho(p_i)} \frac{d\mathcal{H}_x^{n-1}}{|x - \pi_x|^s} \\ &\leq C \int_{\Sigma \cap \{x_{n-1} \in (0, 4\delta)\} \cap \{|(x_1, \dots, x_{n-2})| < 2\rho\}} \frac{dx_1 \dots dx_{n-1}}{|x - \Pi_x|^s}, \end{aligned} \quad (2.11)$$

for a suitable $\Pi_x \in \partial L$ (which is the image of the old projection π_x under this diffeomorphism).

We now observe that the distance of $x = (x_1, \dots, x_{n-1}, 0)$ to ∂L is $\sin \theta x_{n-1}$ and therefore $|x - \Pi_x| \geq \sin \theta x_{n-1}$.

Plugging this information into (2.11), it follows that

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_{\partial E_t \cap \Omega^c \cap T_{2\delta} \cap B_\rho(p_i)} \text{dist}(x, \Omega)^{-s} d\mathcal{H}_x^{n-1} \\ & \leq \frac{C}{\sin^s \theta} \int_{\Sigma \cap \{x_{n-1} \in (0, 4\delta)\} \cap \{|(x_1, \dots, x_{n-2})| < 2\rho\}} \frac{dx_1 \dots dx_{n-1}}{x_{n-1}^s} \leq \frac{C\rho^{n-2}\delta^{1-s}}{\sin^s \theta}, \end{aligned}$$

up to conveniently renaming C .

From this and (2.10), we thus obtain that

$$\left| \int_{\partial E_t \cap \Omega^c \cap T_{2\delta}} \left(\mathcal{A}_{E_t, \Omega}^{K_\delta}(x) - \mathcal{A}_{E_t, \Omega}^K(x) \right) \xi(x) d\mathcal{H}_x^{n-1} \right| \leq \frac{C \|\mathcal{X}\|_{L^\infty(\mathbb{R}^n, \mathbb{R}^n)} \rho^{n-2} \delta^{1-s}}{\sin^s \theta}.$$

Using this and (2.8), we conclude that

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \int_{\partial E_t \cap \Omega^c} \left(\mathcal{A}_{E_t, \Omega}^{K_\delta}(x) - \mathcal{A}_{E_t, \Omega}^K(x) \right) \xi(x) d\mathcal{H}_x^{n-1} \right| \\ & \leq \left| \int_{\partial E_t \cap \Omega^c \cap T_{2\delta}} \left(\mathcal{A}_{E_t, \Omega}^{K_\delta}(x) - \mathcal{A}_{E_t, \Omega}^K(x) \right) \xi(x) d\mathcal{H}_x^{n-1} \right| \\ & \quad + \left| \int_{\partial E_t \cap \Omega^c \cap T_{2\delta}^c} \left(\mathcal{A}_{E_t, \Omega}^{K_\delta}(x) - \mathcal{A}_{E_t, \Omega}^K(x) \right) \xi(x) d\mathcal{H}_x^{n-1} \right| \\ & \leq C \|\mathcal{X}\|_{L^\infty(\mathbb{R}^n, \mathbb{R}^n)} (\delta^{1-s} + \delta^s), \end{aligned}$$

up to relabelling C .

Consequently,

$$\lim_{\delta \searrow 0} \sup_{|t| < \varepsilon} \left| \int_{\partial E_t \cap \Omega^c} \left(\mathcal{A}_{E_t, \Omega}^{K_\delta}(x) - \mathcal{A}_{E_t, \Omega}^K(x) \right) \xi(x) d\mathcal{H}_x^{n-1} \right| \leq \lim_{\delta \searrow 0} \sup_{|t| < \varepsilon} C \|\mathcal{X}\|_\infty \delta^{\min\{s, 1-s\}} = 0.$$

From this, (2.6) and (2.7), we thus obtain that

$$\lim_{\delta \rightarrow 0^+} \sup_{|t| < \varepsilon} \left| \phi'_\delta(t) - \int_{\partial E_t \cap \Omega} \mathcal{H}_{E_t}^K(x) \xi(x) d\mathcal{H}_x^{n-1} - \int_{\partial E_t \cap \Omega^c} \mathcal{A}_{E_t, \Omega}^K(x) \xi(x) d\mathcal{H}_x^{n-1} \right| = 0.$$

As a result, recalling also (2.5) we conclude that, for $|t| < \varepsilon$,

$$\phi'(t) = \int_{\partial E_t \cap \Omega} \mathcal{H}_{E_t}^K(x) \xi(x) d\mathcal{H}_x^{n-1} + \int_{\partial E_t \cap \Omega^c} \mathcal{A}_{E_t, \Omega}^K(x) \xi(x) d\mathcal{H}_x^{n-1},$$

which gives the desired result in (2.4) by taking $t = 0$. \square

3. THE LIMIT OF THE FREE BOUNDARY CONDITION AND PROOF OF THEOREM 1.5

The proof of Theorem 1.5 relies on a straightening procedure, based on two technical results which we state next.

We will consider the following geometric setup: let Ω and F be open sets of class $C^{1,1}$. Let $T: \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^n$ be a diffeomorphism of \mathbb{R}^n of class $C^{1,1}$ and suppose that $T^{-1}(X) = X + S(X)$, with $S(0) = 0$ and $DS(0) = 0$.

For $r \in (0, 1)$, let $Q_r = (-r, r)^n$. Let $U_r := T^{-1}(Q_r)$ and assume that

$$\begin{aligned} T(\Omega \cap U_r) &= \{x_1 < 0\} \cap Q_r, \\ T(F \cap U_r) &= \{\omega \cdot x < 0\} \cap Q_r \end{aligned}$$

with $\omega = (-\sin \vartheta, 0, \dots, 0, \cos \vartheta)$, for some $\vartheta \in (-\frac{\pi}{2}, \frac{\pi}{2})$.

In the remainder of this section, we use uppercase letters (X, Y, \dots) to denote points in the range of T (that is, the straightened domain) and lowercase letters (x, y, \dots) to denote points in the original domain. In particular, we use the notation $X = T(x)$.

We denote

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{J}(X, Y) &:= \frac{X - Y}{|X - Y|} + \frac{DS(X)(X - Y)}{|X - Y|}, \\ \mathcal{W}(X, Y) &:= \frac{D^2S(X)[X - Y, X - Y]}{2|X - Y|}, \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{and } \mathcal{B}_s(X, Y) := -(n + s)|\mathcal{J}(X, Y)|^{-n-s-2} \mathcal{J}(X, Y) \cdot \mathcal{W}(X, Y)$$

Lemma 3.1. *There exist $r_0 \in (0, \frac{1}{2})$ and $C \geq 1$, depending only on Ω , F , ϑ , and n , such that, if $r \in (0, r_0)$, for all $x \in \partial F \cap \Omega^c \cap U_r$,*

$$\begin{aligned} &\left| \int_{\Omega \cap U_r} \frac{\chi_F(y)}{|x - y|^{n+s}} dy - \int_{\{Y_1 < 0\} \cap \{\omega \cdot Y < 0\} \cap Q_r} |\mathcal{J}(X, Y)|^{-n-s} \frac{|\det DT^{-1}(Y)|}{|X - Y|^{n+s}} dY \right. \\ &\quad \left. - \int_{\{Y_1 < 0\} \cap \{\omega \cdot Y < 0\} \cap Q_r} \mathcal{B}_s(X, Y) \frac{|\det DT^{-1}(Y)|}{|X - Y|^{n+s}} dY \right| \\ &\leq \frac{Cr}{s} \left(X_1^{1-s} + \frac{(Cr)^{1-s} - X_1^{1-s}}{1-s} \right). \end{aligned}$$

Proof. By a change of variable, we see that

$$\int_{\Omega \cap U_r} \frac{\chi_F(y)}{|x - y|^{n+s}} dy = \int_{\{Y_1 < 0\} \cap \{\omega \cdot Y < 0\} \cap Q_r} \frac{|\det DT^{-1}(Y)|}{|T^{-1}(X) - T^{-1}(Y)|^{n+s}} dY. \quad (3.1)$$

We observe that, for $|X - Y|$ small,

$$\begin{aligned} |T^{-1}(X) - T^{-1}(Y)|^{-n-s} &= |X - Y + S(X) - S(Y)|^{-n-s} \\ &= \left| X - Y + DS(X)(X - Y) - \frac{D^2S(X)}{2}[X - Y, X - Y] + O(|X - Y|^3) \right|^{-n-s} \\ &= |X - Y|^{-n-s} |\mathcal{J}(X, Y) + \mathcal{W}(X, Y) + O(|X - Y|^2)|^{-n-s}. \end{aligned} \quad (3.2)$$

Moreover, we have that, for small r and $X \in Q_r$,

$$|\mathcal{J}(X, Y)| \geq \frac{1}{2}.$$

Also, for $|X - Y|$ small,

$$\mathcal{W}(X, Y) = O(|X - Y|).$$

Thus,

$$\begin{aligned} & |\mathcal{J}(X, Y) + \mathcal{W}(X, Y) + O(|X - Y|^2)|^{-n-s} \\ &= |\mathcal{J}(X, Y)|^{-n-s} - (n+s)|\mathcal{J}(X, Y)|^{-n-s-2} \mathcal{J}(X, Y) \cdot \mathcal{W}(X, Y) + O(|X - Y|^2). \end{aligned}$$

Using this information into (3.2), we obtain that

$$|T^{-1}(X) - T^{-1}(Y)|^{-n-s} = \frac{|\mathcal{J}(X, Y)|^{-n-s}}{|X - Y|^{n+s}} + \frac{\mathcal{B}_s(X, Y)}{|X - Y|^{n+s}} + O(|X - Y|^{2-n-s}). \quad (3.3)$$

Next, we set

$$\begin{aligned} \Xi(x) &:= \int_{\Omega \cap U_r} \frac{\chi_F(y)}{|x - y|^{n+s}} dy - \int_{\{Y_1 < 0\} \cap \{\omega \cdot Y < 0\} \cap Q_r} |\mathcal{J}(X, Y)|^{-n-s} \frac{|\det DT^{-1}(Y)|}{|X - Y|^{n+s}} dY \\ &\quad - \int_{\{Y_1 < 0\} \cap \{\omega \cdot Y < 0\} \cap Q_r} \mathcal{B}_s(X, Y) \frac{|\det DT^{-1}(Y)|}{|X - Y|^{n+s}} dY. \end{aligned}$$

It follows from (3.1) and (3.3) that

$$|\Xi(x)| \leq C \int_{\{Y_1 < 0\} \cap \{\omega \cdot Y < 0\} \cap Q_r} \frac{dY}{|X - Y|^{n+s-2}}. \quad (3.4)$$

Now we use the notation $Y = (Y_1, Y'', Y_n) \in \mathbb{R} \times \mathbb{R}^{n-2} \times \mathbb{R}$, $\omega_0 = (-\sin \vartheta, \cos \vartheta)$, and $\zeta := (X_1, X_n)$, and we find that

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_{\{Y_1 < 0\} \cap \{\omega \cdot Y < 0\} \cap Q_r} \frac{dY}{|X - Y|^{n+s-2}} \\ &= \int_{\{Y_1 < 0\} \cap \{\omega \cdot Y < 0\} \cap Q_r} \frac{dY}{(|(X_1, X_n) - (Y_1, Y_n)|^2 + |X'' - Y''|^2)^{\frac{n+s-2}{2}}} \\ &\leq \int_{\substack{(\lambda, \mu) \in (-r, r)^2 \times \mathbb{R}^{n-2} \\ \{\lambda_1 < 0\} \cap \{\omega_0 \cdot \lambda < 0\}}} \frac{d\lambda d\mu}{(|\zeta - \lambda|^2 + |\mu|^2)^{\frac{n+s-2}{2}}} \\ &= \int_{\substack{(\lambda, \ell) \in (-r, r)^2 \times \mathbb{R}^{n-2} \\ \{\lambda_1 < 0\} \cap \{\omega_0 \cdot \lambda < 0\}}} \frac{d\lambda d\ell}{|\zeta - \lambda|^s (1 + |\ell|^2)^{\frac{n+s-2}{2}}} \\ &\leq \frac{C}{s} \int_{\substack{\lambda \in (-r, r)^2 \\ \{\lambda_1 < 0\} \cap \{\omega_0 \cdot \lambda < 0\}}} \frac{d\lambda}{|\zeta - \lambda|^s}. \end{aligned} \quad (3.5)$$

We also observe that $X \in T(\partial F \cap U_r)$ and thus $0 = \omega \cdot X = \omega_0 \cdot \zeta$, yielding that

$$\zeta_2 = \zeta_1 \tan \vartheta.$$

Hence, if $\varpi_0 := (\cos \vartheta, \sin \vartheta)$,

$$\zeta \cdot \varpi_0 = \zeta_1 \cos \vartheta + \zeta_2 \sin \vartheta = \frac{\zeta_1}{\cos \vartheta}.$$

Additionally, since $X \in T(\Omega^c \cap U_r)$, we have that $X_1 \geq 0$, thus $\zeta_1 \geq 0$, and consequently $\frac{\zeta_1}{\cos \vartheta} \geq 0$. In particular, if $\lambda_1 < 0$,

$$\frac{2\zeta_1(\lambda \cdot \varpi_0)}{\cos \vartheta} = 2\zeta_1(\lambda_1 + \lambda_2 \tan \vartheta) \leq 2\zeta_1 \lambda_2 \tan \vartheta \leq \zeta_1^2 \tan^2 \vartheta + \lambda_2^2,$$

where the last step relies on the Cauchy–Schwarz inequality.

As a result, since the vectors ω_0 and ϖ_0 constitute an orthonormal basis of \mathbb{R}^2 , if $\lambda_1 < 0$,

$$\begin{aligned} |\zeta - \lambda|^2 &= ((\zeta - \lambda) \cdot \omega_0)^2 + ((\zeta - \lambda) \cdot \varpi_0)^2 = (\lambda \cdot \omega_0)^2 + \left(\frac{\zeta_1}{\cos \vartheta} - \lambda \cdot \varpi_0 \right)^2 \\ &= |\lambda|^2 + \frac{\zeta_1^2}{\cos^2 \vartheta} - \frac{2\zeta_1(\lambda \cdot \varpi_0)}{\cos \vartheta} \geq |\lambda|^2 + \frac{\zeta_1^2}{\cos^2 \vartheta} - \zeta_1^2 \tan^2 \vartheta - \lambda_2^2 \\ &= \lambda_1^2 + \zeta_1^2. \end{aligned}$$

Combining this and (3.5), we see that

$$\begin{aligned} \int_{\{Y_1 < 0\} \cap \{\omega \cdot Y < 0\} \cap Q_r} \frac{dY}{|X - Y|^{n+s}} &\leq \frac{Cr}{s} \int_0^r \frac{d\lambda_1}{(\lambda_1^2 + \zeta_1^2)^{\frac{s}{2}}} \\ &\leq \frac{Cr}{s} \left(\int_0^{\zeta_1} \frac{d\lambda_1}{\zeta_1^s} + \int_{\zeta_1}^r \frac{d\lambda_1}{\lambda_1^s} \right) \leq \frac{Cr}{s} \left(\zeta_1^{1-s} + \frac{r^{1-s} - \zeta_1^{1-s}}{1-s} \right). \end{aligned}$$

This, in tandem with (3.4), returns that

$$|\Xi(x)| \leq \frac{Cr}{s} \left(\zeta_1^{1-s} + \frac{r^{1-s} - \zeta_1^{1-s}}{1-s} \right),$$

as desired. \square

Lemma 3.2. *Let E , Ω , \mathcal{X} and g be as in Theorem 1.5.*

Then, there exists $r_0 \in (0, \frac{1}{2})$, depending only on Ω , E , and n , such that, if $r \in (0, r_0)$,

$$\begin{aligned} \lim_{s \nearrow 1} \int_{\partial E \cap \Omega^c \cap U_r} \mathcal{A}_{E, \Omega}^s(x) \mathcal{X}(x) \cdot \nu_{\partial E}(x) d\mathcal{H}_x^{n-1} \\ = \int_{\partial E \cap \partial \Omega \cap U_r} g(\psi_{x'}) \mathcal{X}(x') \cdot \nu_{\partial E}(x') d\mathcal{H}_{x'}^{n-2} + O(r^{n-1}), \end{aligned}$$

where $\psi_{x'}$ is the intersection angle between the affine hyperplanes $T_{x'}(\partial E)$ and $T_{x'}(\partial \Omega)$.

Proof. We point out that, if $x \in \partial E \cap U_r$,

$$\begin{aligned} |\mathcal{A}_{E,\Omega \setminus U_r}^s(x)| &\leq Cs(1-s) \left| \int_{\Omega \setminus U_r} \frac{\chi_{E^c}(y) - \chi_E(y)}{|x-y|^{n+s}} dy \right| \\ &\leq Cs(1-s) \int_{\mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_r} \frac{dz}{|z|^{n+s}} \\ &\leq \frac{C(1-s)}{r^s}. \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, by the Dominated Convergence Theorem,

$$\lim_{s \nearrow 1} \int_{\partial E \cap \Omega^c \cap U_r} \mathcal{A}_{E,\Omega \setminus U_r}^s(x) \mathcal{X}(x) \cdot \nu_{\partial E}(x) d\mathcal{H}_x^{n-1} = 0.$$

As a result, since

$$\mathcal{A}_{E,\Omega}^s = \mathcal{A}_{E,\Omega \setminus U_r}^s + \mathcal{A}_{E,\Omega \cap U_r}^s,$$

we conclude that

$$\begin{aligned} \lim_{s \nearrow 1} \int_{\partial E \cap \Omega^c \cap U_r} \mathcal{A}_{E,\Omega}^s(x) \mathcal{X}(x) \cdot \nu_{\partial E}(x) d\mathcal{H}_x^{n-1} \\ = \lim_{s \nearrow 1} \int_{\partial E \cap \Omega^c \cap U_r} \mathcal{A}_{E,\Omega \cap U_r}^s(x) \mathcal{X}(x) \cdot \nu_{\partial E}(x) d\mathcal{H}_x^{n-1}. \end{aligned} \quad (3.6)$$

Now, we utilize the coarea formula on manifolds, see [Mor00, Theorem 3.13], and we have that

$$\begin{aligned} \int_{\partial E \cap \Omega^c \cap U_r} \mathcal{A}_{E,\Omega \cap U_r}^s(x) \mathcal{X}(x) \cdot \nu_{\partial E}(x) d\mathcal{H}_x^{n-1} \\ = \int_{\{\omega \cdot X = 0\} \cap \{X_1 > 0\} \cap Q_r} \mathcal{A}_{E,\Omega \cap U_r}^s(x) \mathcal{V}(x) d\mathcal{H}_X^{n-1}, \end{aligned} \quad (3.7)$$

where the notation $X = T(x)$ is understood and we have set, for convenience,

$$\mathcal{V}(x) := \frac{\mathcal{X}(x) \cdot \nu_{\partial E}(x)}{|\det DT|_{\partial E}(x)|},$$

with $T|_{\partial E}: \partial E \cap U_r \rightarrow \{\omega \cdot X = 0\} \cap Q_r$ being the restriction of T to ∂E .

Furthermore, we apply Lemma 3.1 with $F := E$ and $F := E^c$ (in the latter case, ω gets replaced by $-\omega$). Thus, up to renaming $C > 0$, we find that

$$\begin{aligned} |\mathcal{A}_{E,\Omega \cap U_r}^s(x) - c_{n,s}(\mathcal{J}_1(X) + \mathcal{J}_2(X))| \\ = c_{n,s} \left| \int_{\Omega \cap U_r} \frac{\chi_{E^c}(y) - \chi_E(y)}{|x-y|^{n+s}} dy - \mathcal{J}_1(X) - \mathcal{J}_2(X) \right| \\ \leq C(1-s)r \left(X_1^{1-s} + \frac{(Cr)^{1-s} - X_1^{1-s}}{1-s} \right), \end{aligned} \quad (3.8)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{J}_1(X) &:= \int_{\{Y_1 < 0\} \cap \{\omega \cdot Y > 0\} \cap Q_r} |\mathcal{I}(X, Y)|^{-n-s} \frac{|\det DT^{-1}(Y)|}{|X - Y|^{n+s}} dY \\ &\quad - \int_{\{Y_1 < 0\} \cap \{\omega \cdot Y < 0\} \cap Q_r} |\mathcal{I}(X, Y)|^{-n-s} \frac{|\det DT^{-1}(Y)|}{|X - Y|^{n+s}} dY \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{J}_2(X) &:= \int_{\{Y_1 < 0\} \cap \{\omega \cdot Y > 0\} \cap Q_r} \mathcal{B}_s(X, Y) \frac{|\det DT^{-1}(Y)|}{|X - Y|^{n+s}} dY \\ &\quad - \int_{\{Y_1 < 0\} \cap \{\omega \cdot Y < 0\} \cap Q_r} \mathcal{B}_s(X, Y) \frac{|\det DT^{-1}(Y)|}{|X - Y|^{n+s}} dY. \end{aligned}$$

As a consequence of (3.7) and (3.8), we find that, up to renaming $C > 0$ line after line,

$$\begin{aligned} &\left| \int_{\partial E \cap \Omega^c \cap U_r} \mathcal{A}_{E, \Omega \cap U_r}^s(x) \mathcal{X}(x) \cdot \nu_{\partial E}(x) d\mathcal{H}_x^{n-1} \right. \\ &\quad \left. - c_{n,s} \int_{\{\omega \cdot X = 0\} \cap \{X_1 > 0\} \cap Q_r} (\mathcal{J}_1(X) + \mathcal{J}_2(X)) \mathcal{V}(x) d\mathcal{H}_X^{n-1} \right| \\ &\leq C(1-s)r \int_{\{\omega \cdot X = 0\} \cap \{X_1 > 0\} \cap Q_r} \left(X_1^{1-s} + \frac{(Cr)^{1-s} - X_1^{1-s}}{1-s} \right) |\mathcal{V}(x)| d\mathcal{H}_X^{n-1} \\ &\leq Cr \int_{\{\omega \cdot X = 0\} \cap \{X_1 > 0\} \cap Q_r \cap \text{spt } \mathcal{X}} \left((1-s)r^{1-s} + (Cr)^{1-s} - X_1^{1-s} \right) d\mathcal{H}_X^{n-1}. \end{aligned}$$

We observe that this quantity is infinitesimal as $s \nearrow 1$, thanks to the Dominated Convergence Theorem, and as a result we obtain that

$$\begin{aligned} &\lim_{s \nearrow 1} \int_{\partial E \cap \Omega^c \cap U_r} \mathcal{A}_{E, \Omega \cap U_r}^s(x) \mathcal{X}(x) \cdot \nu_{\partial E}(x) d\mathcal{H}_x^{n-1} \\ &= \lim_{s \nearrow 1} c_{n,s} \int_{\{\omega \cdot X = 0\} \cap \{X_1 > 0\} \cap Q_r} (\mathcal{J}_1(X) + \mathcal{J}_2(X)) \mathcal{V}(x) d\mathcal{H}_X^{n-1}. \end{aligned} \tag{3.9}$$

We remark that, thanks to the fact that $DS(0) = 0$, we have that, if $X \in Q_r$,

$$||\mathcal{I}(X, Y)|^{-n-s} - 1| \leq Cr,$$

for some $C > 0$ uniform with respect to $X, Y \in Q_r$.

Hence, setting $\mathcal{J}_*(X) := \mathcal{J}_*^1(X) - \mathcal{J}_*^2(X)$, with

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{J}_*^1(X) &:= \int_{\{Y_1 < 0\} \cap \{\omega \cdot Y > 0\} \cap Q_r} \frac{|\det DT^{-1}(Y)|}{|X - Y|^{n+s}} dY \\ \text{and } \mathcal{J}_*^2(X) &:= \int_{\{Y_1 < 0\} \cap \{\omega \cdot Y < 0\} \cap Q_r} \frac{|\det DT^{-1}(Y)|}{|X - Y|^{n+s}} dY, \end{aligned}$$

we find that

$$\begin{aligned}
& |\mathcal{J}_1(X) - \mathcal{J}_*(X)| \\
&= \left| \int_{\{Y_1 < 0\} \cap \{\omega \cdot Y > 0\} \cap Q_r} |\mathcal{J}(X, Y)|^{-n-s} \frac{|\det DT^{-1}(Y)|}{|X - Y|^{n+s}} dY - \mathcal{J}_*^1(X) \right. \\
&\quad \left. - \int_{\{Y_1 < 0\} \cap \{\omega \cdot Y < 0\} \cap Q_r} |\mathcal{J}(X, Y)|^{-n-s} \frac{|\det DT^{-1}(Y)|}{|X - Y|^{n+s}} dY + \mathcal{J}_*^2(X) \right| \\
&\leq \left| \int_{\{Y_1 < 0\} \cap \{\omega \cdot Y > 0\} \cap Q_r} \left| |\mathcal{J}(X, Y)|^{-n-s} - 1 \right| \frac{|\det DT^{-1}(Y)|}{|X - Y|^{n+s}} dY \right| \\
&\quad + \left| \int_{\{Y_1 < 0\} \cap \{\omega \cdot Y < 0\} \cap Q_r} \left| |\mathcal{J}(X, Y)|^{-n-s} - 1 \right| \frac{|\det DT^{-1}(Y)|}{|X - Y|^{n+s}} dY \right| \\
&\leq Cr \int_{\{Y_1 < 0\} \cap \{\omega \cdot Y > 0\} \cap Q_r} \frac{|\det DT^{-1}(Y)|}{|X - Y|^{n+s}} dY \\
&\quad + Cr \int_{\{Y_1 < 0\} \cap \{\omega \cdot Y < 0\} \cap Q_r} \frac{|\det DT^{-1}(Y)|}{|X - Y|^{n+s}} dY.
\end{aligned} \tag{3.10}$$

Furthermore, by (3.6) and (3.9) we get that

$$\lim_{s \nearrow 1} \int_{\partial E \cap \Omega^c \cap U_r} \mathcal{A}_{E, \Omega}^s(x) \mathcal{X}(x) \cdot \nu_{\partial E}(x) d\mathcal{H}_x^{n-1} = \text{I} + \text{II} + \text{III} \tag{3.11}$$

where

$$\begin{aligned}
\text{I} &:= \lim_{s \nearrow 1} c_{n,s} \int_{\{\omega \cdot X = 0\} \cap \{X_1 > 0\} \cap Q_r} \mathcal{J}_*(X) \mathcal{V}(x) d\mathcal{H}_X^{n-1}, \\
\text{II} &:= \lim_{s \nearrow 1} c_{n,s} \int_{\{\omega \cdot X = 0\} \cap \{X_1 > 0\} \cap Q_r} (\mathcal{J}_1(X) - \mathcal{J}_*(X)) \mathcal{V}(x) d\mathcal{H}_X^{n-1}, \\
\text{and III} &:= \lim_{s \nearrow 1} c_{n,s} \int_{\{\omega \cdot X = 0\} \cap \{X_1 > 0\} \cap Q_r} \mathcal{J}_2(X) \mathcal{V}(x) d\mathcal{H}_X^{n-1}.
\end{aligned}$$

We now write $\text{I} = \text{I}_1 - \text{I}_2$, where, for $k \in \{1, 2\}$,

$$\text{I}_k := \lim_{s \nearrow 1} c_{n,s} \int_{\{\omega \cdot X = 0\} \cap \{X_1 > 0\} \cap Q_r} \mathcal{J}_*^k(X) \mathcal{V}(x) d\mathcal{H}_X^{n-1}.$$

Note that, for every $\rho_0 > 0$,

$$\lim_{s \nearrow 1} c_{n,s} \int_{\{\omega \cdot X = 0\} \cap \{X_1 > 0\} \cap Q_r} \left(\int_{\mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_{\rho_0}(X)} \frac{dY}{|X - Y|^{n+s}} \right) |\mathcal{V}(x)| d\mathcal{H}_X^{n-1} \leq \lim_{s \nearrow 1} \frac{C(1-s)}{s\rho_0^s} = 0$$

and therefore

$$\begin{aligned}
& \lim_{s \nearrow 1} c_{n,s} \int_{\{\omega \cdot X=0\} \cap \{X_1>0\} \cap Q_r} \mathcal{J}_*^1(X) \mathcal{V}(x) d\mathcal{H}_X^{n-1}, \\
&= \lim_{s \nearrow 1} c_{n,s} \int_{\substack{\{\omega \cdot X=0\} \\ \{X_1>0\} \cap Q_{r/2}}} \left(\int_{\substack{\{Y_1<0\} \\ \{\omega \cdot Y>0\} \cap Q_r}} \frac{|\det DT^{-1}(Y)|}{|X-Y|^{n+s}} dY \right) \mathcal{V}(x) d\mathcal{H}_X^{n-1} \\
&= \lim_{s \nearrow 1} c_{n,s} \int_{\substack{\{\omega \cdot X=0\} \\ \{X_1>0\} \cap Q_r}} \left(\int_{\substack{\{Y_1<0\} \\ \{\omega \cdot Y>0\}}} \frac{|\det DT^{-1}(Y)|}{|X-Y|^{n+s}} dY \right) \mathcal{V}(x) d\mathcal{H}_X^{n-1}.
\end{aligned}$$

Hence, if we use the substitution $W := (Y_1, Y_2 - X_2, \dots, Y_n - X_n) = Y - X + X_1 e_1$, we see that

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbb{I}_1 &= \lim_{s \nearrow 1} c_{n,s} \int_{\{\omega \cdot X=0\} \cap \{X_1>0\} \cap Q_r} \mathcal{J}_*^1(X) \mathcal{V}(x) d\mathcal{H}_X^{n-1} \\
&= \lim_{s \nearrow 1} c_{n,s} \int_{\{\omega \cdot X=0\} \cap \{X_1>0\} \cap Q_r} \left(\int_{\substack{\{W_1<0\} \\ \{\omega \cdot W + X_1 \sin \vartheta > 0\}}} \frac{|\det DT^{-1}(W + X - X_1 e_1)|}{|W - X_1 e_1|^{n+s}} dW \right) \mathcal{V}(x) d\mathcal{H}_X^{n-1}.
\end{aligned}$$

Accordingly, substituting for $Z := \frac{W}{X_1}$ and letting $\omega_0 := (-\sin \vartheta, \cos \vartheta)$,

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbb{I}_1 &= \lim_{s \nearrow 1} c_{n,s} \int_{\{\omega \cdot X=0\} \cap \{X_1>0\} \cap Q_r} \left(\int_{\substack{\{Z_1<0\} \\ \{\omega \cdot Z + \sin \vartheta > 0\}}} \frac{|\det DT^{-1}(X_1 Z + X - X_1 e_1)|}{|Z - e_1|^{n+s}} dZ \right) \frac{\mathcal{V}(x) d\mathcal{H}_X^{n-1}}{X_1^s} \\
&= \lim_{s \nearrow 1} c_{n,s} \int_{\{\omega_0 \cdot \zeta=0\} \cap \{\zeta_1>0\} \cap Q_r} \left(\int_{\substack{\{Z_1<0\} \\ \{\omega \cdot Z + \sin \vartheta > 0\}}} \frac{|\det DT^{-1}(\zeta_1 Z + X - \zeta_1 e_1)|}{|Z - e_1|^{n+s}} dZ \right) \frac{\mathcal{V}(x) d\mathcal{H}_X^{n-1}}{\zeta_1^s} \\
&= \lim_{s \nearrow 1} c_{n,s} \int_{\{\omega_0 \cdot \zeta=0\} \cap \{\zeta_1>0\} \cap Q_r} \mathcal{G}_s(\zeta, X'') \mathcal{V}(x) \frac{d\mathcal{H}_\zeta^1 d\mathcal{H}_{X''}^{n-2}}{\zeta_1^s} \\
&= \lim_{s \nearrow 1} c_{n,s} \int_{\{\zeta_1>0\} \cap \{\zeta_2=\zeta_1 \tan \vartheta\} \cap Q_r} \mathcal{G}_s(\zeta, X'') \mathcal{V}(x) \frac{d\zeta_1 d\mathcal{H}_{X''}^{n-2}}{\zeta_1^s},
\end{aligned}$$

where we use the intermediate notation $X = (\zeta_1, X'', \zeta_2) \in \mathbb{R} \times \mathbb{R}^{n-2} \times \mathbb{R}$ and $\zeta = (\zeta_1, \zeta_2) \in \mathbb{R}^2$ and set

$$\mathcal{G}_s(\zeta, X'') := \int_{\substack{\{Z_1<0\} \\ \{\omega \cdot Z + \sin \vartheta > 0\}}} \frac{|\det DT^{-1}(\zeta_1 Z + X - \zeta_1 e_1)|}{|Z - e_1|^{n+s}} dZ.$$

It is now convenient to change variable $\tau := \zeta_1^{1-s}$ to find that

$$\mathbb{I}_1 = \lim_{s \nearrow 1} \int_{\substack{\{\tau \in (0, r^{1-s})\} \cap \{\zeta_2 = \tau^{1/(1-s)} \tan \vartheta\} \\ \cap \{|\zeta_2| < r\} \cap \{|X''|_\infty < r\}}} \mathcal{G}_s(\tau^{1/(1-s)}, \zeta_2, X'') \mathcal{V}(x) d\tau d\mathcal{H}_{X''}^{n-2}.$$

Since \mathcal{G}_s is bounded uniformly in s (and compactly supported, since so is \mathcal{X}), we can now use the Dominated Convergence Theorem and conclude that

$$\begin{aligned}
I_1 &= \int_{\{\tau \in (0,1)\} \cap \{|X''|_\infty < r\}} \mathcal{G}_1(0,0,X'') \mathcal{V}(T^{-1}(0,X'',0)) d\tau d\mathcal{H}_{X''}^{n-2} \\
&= \int_{\{|X''|_\infty < r\}} \mathcal{G}_1(0,0,X'') \mathcal{V}(T^{-1}(0,X'',0)) d\mathcal{H}_{X''}^{n-2} \\
&= \int_{\{|X''|_\infty < r\}} \left(\int_{\substack{\{Z_1 < 0\} \\ \{\omega \cdot Z + \sin \vartheta > 0\}}} \frac{|\det DT^{-1}(0,X'',0)|}{|Z - e_1|^{n+s}} dZ \right) \frac{\mathcal{X}(T^{-1}(0,X'',0)) \cdot \nu_{\partial E}(T^{-1}(0,X'',0))}{|\det DT(T^{-1}(0,X'',0))|} d\mathcal{H}_{X''}^{n-2} \\
&= \int_{\{|X''|_\infty < r\}} \left(\int_{\substack{\{Z_1 < 0\} \\ \{\omega \cdot Z + \sin \vartheta > 0\}}} \frac{dZ}{|Z - e_1|^{n+s}} \right) \mathcal{X}(T^{-1}(0,X'',0)) \cdot \nu_{\partial E}(T^{-1}(0,X'',0)) d\mathcal{H}_{X''}^{n-2}.
\end{aligned} \tag{3.12}$$

Along the same vein,

$$I_2 = \int_{\{|X''|_\infty < r\}} \left(\int_{\substack{\{Z_1 < 0\} \\ \{\omega \cdot Z + \sin \vartheta < 0\}}} \frac{dZ}{|Z - e_1|^{n+s}} \right) \mathcal{X}(T^{-1}(0,X'',0)) \cdot \nu_{\partial E}(T^{-1}(0,X'',0)) d\mathcal{H}_{X''}^{n-2}. \tag{3.13}$$

Furthermore, if $\tilde{\omega} := (\sin \vartheta, 0, \dots, 0, \cos \vartheta)$ and $\tilde{Z} := (Z_1, \dots, Z_{n-1}, -Z_n)$,

$$\begin{aligned}
&\int_{\substack{\{Z_1 < 0\} \\ \{\tilde{\omega} \cdot Z - \sin \vartheta > 0\}}} \frac{dZ}{|Z - e_1|^{n+s}} = \int_{\substack{\{Z_1 < 0\} \\ \{Z_1 \sin \vartheta + Z_n \cos \vartheta - \sin \vartheta > 0\}}} \frac{dZ}{|Z - e_1|^{n+s}} \\
&= \int_{\substack{\{\tilde{Z}_1 < 0\} \\ \{\tilde{\omega} \cdot \tilde{Z} - \sin \vartheta < 0\}}} \frac{d\tilde{Z}}{|\tilde{Z} - e_1|^{n+s}} = \int_{\substack{\{\tilde{Z}_1 < 0\} \\ \{\omega \cdot \tilde{Z} + \sin \vartheta < 0\}}} \frac{d\tilde{Z}}{|\tilde{Z} - e_1|^{n+s}},
\end{aligned}$$

leading to

$$\begin{aligned}
&\int_{\substack{\{Z_1 < 0\} \\ \{\omega \cdot Z + \sin \vartheta > 0\}}} \frac{dZ}{|Z - e_1|^{n+s}} - \int_{\substack{\{Z_1 < 0\} \\ \{\omega \cdot Z + \sin \vartheta < 0\}}} \frac{dZ}{|Z - e_1|^{n+s}} \\
&= \int_{\substack{\{Z_1 < 0\} \\ \{\omega \cdot Z + \sin \vartheta > 0\} \\ \{\tilde{\omega} \cdot Z - \sin \vartheta < 0\}}} \frac{dZ}{|Z - e_1|^{n+s}} = \int_{\substack{\{Z_1 < 0\} \\ \{Z_n \in ((Z_1 - 1) \tan \vartheta, (1 - Z_1) \tan \vartheta)\}}} \frac{dZ}{|Z - e_1|^{n+s}}.
\end{aligned}$$

Using this, together with (3.12) and (3.13), we find that

$$I = \int_{\{|X''|_\infty < r\}} \left(\int_{\substack{\{Z_1 < 0\} \\ \{Z_n \in ((Z_1 - 1) \tan \vartheta, (1 - Z_1) \tan \vartheta)\}}} \frac{dZ}{|Z - e_1|^{n+s}} \right) \mathcal{X}(T^{-1}(0,X'',0)) \cdot \nu_{\partial E}(T^{-1}(0,X'',0)) d\mathcal{H}_{X''}^{n-2}.$$

We observe that, setting $\psi := \frac{\pi}{2} - \vartheta$,

$$\int_{\substack{\{Z_1 < 0\} \\ \{Z_n \in ((Z_1 - 1) \tan \vartheta, (1 - Z_1) \tan \vartheta)\}}} \frac{dZ}{|Z - e_1|^{n+s}} = g(\psi),$$

and so

$$\text{I} = \int_{\{|X''|_\infty < r\}} g(\psi) \mathcal{X}(T^{-1}(0, X'', 0)) \cdot \nu_{\partial E}(T^{-1}(0, X'', 0)) d\mathcal{H}_{X''}^{n-2}.$$

Now, using the coarea formula on manifolds, see [Mor00, Theorem 3.13], we get that

$$\text{I} = \int_{\partial E \cap \partial \Omega \cap U_r} g(\psi) \mathcal{X}(x'') \cdot \nu_{\partial E}(x'') |\det DT|_{\partial E \cap \partial \Omega}(x'') d\mathcal{H}_{x''}^{n-2},$$

with the notation $x'' = T^{-1}(0, X'', 0)$.

Note that by smoothness of g we have

$$|g(\psi) - g(\psi_{x''})| \leq C|x''| \leq Cr$$

and similarly, since T is the identity in the origin,

$$|1 - |\det DT|_{\partial E \cap \partial \Omega}(x'')|| \leq C|x''| \leq Cr.$$

Also, by the regularity of $\partial E \cap \partial \Omega$ we have

$$\mathcal{H}^{n-2}(\partial E \cap \partial \Omega \cap U_r) = O(r^{n-2}).$$

All in all, we obtain that

$$\text{I} = \int_{\partial E \cap \partial \Omega \cap U_r} g(\psi_{x''}) \mathcal{X}(x'') \cdot \nu_{\partial E}(x'') d\mathcal{H}_{x''}^{n-2} + O(r^{n-1}). \quad (3.14)$$

We now take care of the term II. For this, we observe that

$$\text{if } X_1 > 0 > Y_1 \text{ then } |X - Y| \geq X_1 - Y_1 \geq X_1, \quad (3.15)$$

and therefore

$$\int_{\{Y_1 < 0\} \cap Q_r} \frac{dY}{|X - Y|^{n+s}} \leq \int_{|X - Y| \geq X_1} \frac{dY}{|X - Y|^{n+s}} \leq \frac{C}{sX_1^s}.$$

From this and (3.10) we deduce that

$$|\mathcal{J}_1(X) - \mathcal{J}_*(X)| \leq \frac{Cr}{sX_1^s}.$$

As a result,

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \int_{\{\omega \cdot X = 0\} \cap \{X_1 > 0\} \cap Q_r} (\mathcal{J}_1(X) - \mathcal{J}_*(X)) \mathcal{V}(x) d\mathcal{H}_X^{n-1} \right| \\ & \leq \frac{Cr}{s} \int_{\{\omega \cdot X = 0\} \cap \{X_1 > 0\} \cap Q_r} \frac{d\mathcal{H}_X^{n-1}}{X_1^s} \leq \frac{Cr^{n-1}}{s} \int_0^r \frac{dX_1}{X_1^s} = \frac{Cr^{n-s}}{s(1-s)} \end{aligned}$$

and thus

$$\text{II} = O(r^{n-1}). \quad (3.16)$$

To estimate III, note that $|\mathcal{B}_s(X, Y)| \leq C|X - Y|$ and therefore

$$|\mathcal{J}_2(X)| \leq C \int_{\{Y_1 < 0\} \cap Q_r} \frac{dY}{|X - Y|^{n+s-1}}.$$

Recalling also (3.15) we thereby obtain that

$$|\mathcal{J}_2(X)| \leq C \int_{|X-Y| \geq X_1} \frac{dY}{|X-Y|^{n+s-1}} \leq \frac{CX_1^{1-s}}{1-s}.$$

It follows that

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| c_{n,s} \int_{\{\omega \cdot X = 0\} \cap \{X_1 > 0\} \cap Q_r} \mathcal{J}_2(X) \mathcal{V}(x) d\mathcal{H}_X^{n-1} \right| \\ & \leq C \int_{\{\omega \cdot X = 0\} \cap \{X_1 > 0\} \cap Q_r} X_1^{1-s} d\mathcal{H}_X^{n-1} \\ & \leq Cr^{1-s} \mathcal{H}^{n-1}(\{\omega \cdot X = 0\} \cap \{X_1 > 0\} \cap Q_r) \\ & \leq Cr^{1-s+n-1} \\ & \leq Cr^{n-1} \end{aligned}$$

from which we deduce that

$$\text{III} = O(r^{n-1}). \quad (3.17)$$

Gathering together (3.14), (3.16) and (3.17), and recalling (3.11), we obtain the desired result. \square

With Lemma 3.2 we can now complete the proof of Theorem 1.5.

Proof of Theorem 1.5. The proof follows from a covering argument, whose details are as follows.

Given $r > 0$ sufficiently small, we denote by $T_r(\partial E \cap \partial \Omega)$ the r -tubular neighbourhood of $\partial E \cap \partial \Omega$ obtained by local diffeomorphisms with Q_r as described at the beginning of Section 3. More precisely, we consider a collection of disjoint open sets U_r^j , with $j = 1, \dots, N_r$, such that

$$T_r(\partial E \cap \partial \Omega) = \bigcup_{j=1}^{N_r} U_r^j =: U_r,$$

up to sets of null measure. We point out that $N_r = O(r^{2-n})$.

By Lemma 3.2, we have that

$$\begin{aligned}
& \lim_{s \nearrow 1} \int_{\partial E \cap \Omega^c \cap U_r} \mathcal{A}_{E,\Omega}^s(x) \mathcal{X}(x) \cdot \nu_{\partial E}(x) d\mathcal{H}_x^{n-1} \\
&= \lim_{s \nearrow 1} \sum_{j=1}^{N_r} \int_{\partial E \cap \Omega^c \cap U_r} \mathcal{A}_{E,\Omega}^s(x) \mathcal{X}(x) \cdot \nu_{\partial E}(x) d\mathcal{H}_x^{n-1} \\
&= \sum_{j=1}^{N_r} \int_{\partial E \cap \partial \Omega \cap U_r} g(\psi_{x'}) \mathcal{X}(x') \cdot \nu_{\partial E}(x') d\mathcal{H}_{x'}^{n-2} + O(N_r r^{n-1}) \\
&= \int_{\partial E \cap \partial \Omega \cap U_r} g(\psi_{x'}) \mathcal{X}(x') \cdot \nu_{\partial E}(x') d\mathcal{H}_{x'}^{n-2} + O(N_r r^{n-1}) \\
&= \int_{\partial E \cap \partial \Omega} g(\psi_{x'}) \mathcal{X}(x') \cdot \nu_{\partial E}(x') d\mathcal{H}_{x'}^{n-2} + O(r).
\end{aligned} \tag{3.18}$$

We also observe that

$$\lim_{s \nearrow 1} \left| \int_{(\partial E \cap \Omega^c) \setminus U_r} \mathcal{A}_{E,\Omega}^s(x) \mathcal{X}(x) \cdot \nu_{\partial E}(x) d\mathcal{H}_x^{n-1} \right| \leq \lim_{s \nearrow 1} \frac{C c_{n,s}}{r^{n+s}} = 0.$$

From this and (3.18), we infer that

$$\lim_{s \nearrow 1} \int_{\partial E \cap \Omega^c} \mathcal{A}_{E,\Omega}^s(x) \mathcal{X}(x) \cdot \nu_{\partial E}(x) d\mathcal{H}_x^{n-1} = \int_{\partial E \cap \partial \Omega} g(\psi_{x'}) \mathcal{X}(x') \cdot \nu_{\partial E}(x') d\mathcal{H}_{x'}^{n-2} + O(r).$$

The desired result now follows by sending $r \searrow 0$. \square

4. FREE BOUNDARIES WITHOUT FREE BOUNDARIES AND PROOF OF THEOREM 1.7

Here we construct an example of free boundary nonlocal minimal surface E in the unit ball such that $\partial E \cap \partial \Omega = \emptyset$, proving Theorem 1.7. We begin our construction with the following preliminary result.

Lemma 4.1. *For any $s \in (0, 1)$ there exists $R_* = R_*(s) > 1$ such that*

$$\mathcal{H}_{B_{R_*} \setminus B_1}^s(x) = 0 \quad \text{for } x \in \partial B_1. \tag{4.1}$$

Moreover,

$$\lim_{s \searrow 0} R_*(s) = +\infty. \tag{4.2}$$

Proof. We point out that, by symmetry, the claim in (4.1) is established if we show that

$$\mathcal{H}_{B_{R_*} \setminus B_1}^s(e_1) = 0.$$

To check this, we define

$$f_s(R) := \mathcal{H}_{B_R \setminus B_1}^s(e_1) = c_{n,s} \text{ p. v. } \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} \frac{\chi_{(B_R \setminus B_1)^c}(y) - \chi_{B_R \setminus B_1}(y)}{|e_1 - y|^{n+s}} dy.$$

First, note that f is continuous in $(1, +\infty)$. Indeed, for any $1 < R_1 \leq R_2$,

$$|f_s(R_1) - f_s(R_2)| = 2c_{n,s} \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} \frac{\chi_{B_{R_2} \setminus B_{R_1}}(y)}{|e_1 - y|^{n+s}} dy \leq \frac{2c_{n,s}\omega_n}{(R_1 - 1)^{n+s}} (R_2^n - R_1^n)$$

from which continuity follows.

Next, we observe that

$$\lim_{R \searrow 1} f_s(R) \in (0, +\infty]. \quad (4.3)$$

Indeed,

$$\begin{aligned} \lim_{R \searrow 1} f_s(R) &= \lim_{R \searrow 1} c_{n,s} \text{p. v.} \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} \frac{\chi_{B_R^c}(y) + \chi_{B_1}(y) - \chi_{B_R \setminus B_1}(y)}{|e_1 - y|^{n+s}} dy \\ &= c_{n,s} \text{p. v.} \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} \frac{\chi_{B_1^c}(y) + \chi_{B_1}(y)}{|e_1 - y|^{n+s}} dy = c_{n,s} \text{p. v.} \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} \frac{dy}{|e_1 - y|^{n+s}}, \end{aligned}$$

which proves (4.3).

Moreover,

$$\lim_{R \nearrow +\infty} f_s(R) < 0. \quad (4.4)$$

Indeed,

$$\begin{aligned} \lim_{R \nearrow +\infty} f_s(R) &= \lim_{R \nearrow +\infty} c_{n,s} \text{p. v.} \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} \frac{\chi_{(B_R \setminus B_1)^c}(y) - \chi_{B_R \setminus B_1}(y)}{|e_1 - y|^{n+s}} dy \\ &= c_{n,s} \text{p. v.} \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} \frac{\chi_{B_1}(y) - \chi_{\mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_1}(y)}{|e_1 - y|^{n+s}} dy = -\mathcal{H}_{B_1}^s(e_1) < 0, \end{aligned}$$

which is (4.4).

As a consequence of (4.3) and (4.4), by continuity, there must exist $R_* = R_*(s) > 1$ such that $f_s(R_*) = 0$, namely $\mathcal{H}_{B_{R_*} \setminus B_1}^s(e_1) = 0$, as desired.

To prove (4.2), we first claim that

$$\text{for any } R > 1 \text{ there exists } s_0 \in (0, 1) \text{ such that if } s \in (0, s_0) \text{ then } f_s(R) > 0. \quad (4.5)$$

For this, we write

$$f_s(R) = \text{I}_s + \text{II}_s,$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} \text{I}_s &:= c_{n,s} \text{p. v.} \int_{B_{2R}(e_1)} \frac{\chi_{(B_R \setminus B_1)^c}(y) - \chi_{B_R \setminus B_1}(y)}{|e_1 - y|^{n+s}} dy \\ \text{and } \text{II}_s &:= c_{n,s} \int_{B_{2R}^c(e_1)} \frac{dy}{|e_1 - y|^{n+s}}. \end{aligned}$$

We take $\lambda \in (0, R - 1)$ and we notice that

$$\begin{aligned} \left| \int_{B_{2R}(e_1) \setminus B_\lambda(e_1)} \frac{\chi_{(B_R \setminus B_1)^c}(y) - \chi_{B_R \setminus B_1}(y)}{|e_1 - y|^{n+s}} dy \right| &\leq 2 \int_{B_{2R}(e_1) \setminus B_\lambda(e_1)} \frac{dy}{|e_1 - y|^{n+s}} \\ &= \frac{2\omega_n}{s} \left(\frac{1}{\lambda^s} - \frac{1}{(2R)^s} \right). \end{aligned} \quad (4.6)$$

Moreover, we observe that if $y \in B_\lambda(e_1)$ then

$$|y| \leq |y - e_1| + 1 < \lambda + 1 < R.$$

Therefore

$$\begin{aligned} \int_{B_\lambda(e_1)} \frac{\chi_{(B_R \setminus B_1)^c}(y) - \chi_{B_R \setminus B_1}(y)}{|e_1 - y|^{n+s}} dy &= \int_{B_\lambda(e_1)} \frac{\chi_{B_1}(y) - \chi_{B_R \setminus B_1}(y)}{|e_1 - y|^{n+s}} dy \\ &= - \int_{B_\lambda(e_1) \cap P_\lambda} \frac{dy}{|e_1 - y|^{n+s}}, \end{aligned}$$

where

$$P_\lambda := \left\{ x = (x_1, x') \in \mathbb{R}^n \text{ s.t. } |x'| < \lambda \text{ and } |x_1 - 1| \leq \lambda - \sqrt{\lambda^2 - |x'|^2} \right\}.$$

Hence, by [DSV16, Lemma 3.1] we conclude that

$$\left| \int_{B_\lambda(e_1)} \frac{\chi_{(B_R \setminus B_1)^c}(y) - \chi_{B_R \setminus B_1}(y)}{|e_1 - y|^{n+s}} dy \right| \leq \frac{C}{(1-s)\lambda^s},$$

for some $C > 0$ depending only on n .

From this and (4.6), we gather that

$$\left| \int_{B_{2R}(e_1)} \frac{\chi_{(B_R \setminus B_1)^c}(y) - \chi_{B_R \setminus B_1}(y)}{|e_1 - y|^{n+s}} dy \right| \leq \frac{2\omega_n}{s} \left(\frac{1}{\lambda^s} - \frac{1}{(2R)^s} \right) + \frac{C}{(1-s)\lambda^s}.$$

As a result,

$$|I_s| \leq \frac{2\omega_n c_{n,s}}{s} \left(\frac{1}{\lambda^s} - \frac{1}{(2R)^s} \right) + \frac{C c_{n,s}}{(1-s)\lambda^s}.$$

Thus, exploiting the limits in (1.9),

$$\lim_{s \searrow 0} |I_s| \leq \lim_{s \searrow 0} \frac{2\omega_n c_{n,s}}{s} \left(\frac{1}{\lambda^s} - \frac{1}{(2R)^s} \right) + \frac{C c_{n,s}}{(1-s)\lambda^s} = 0. \quad (4.7)$$

Furthermore, changing variable $z := y - e_1$,

$$\Pi_s = c_{n,s} \int_{B_{2R}^c} \frac{dz}{|z|^{n+s}} = \frac{c_{n,s} \omega_n}{s(2R)^s}$$

and therefore, recalling also the first limit in (1.9),

$$\lim_{s \searrow 0} \Pi_s = \lim_{s \searrow 0} \frac{c_{n,s} \omega_n}{s(2R)^s} = 8.$$

From this and (4.7), we obtain the desired claim in (4.5).

Also, we point out that f_s is a decreasing function in $(1, +\infty)$. Consequently, if $f_s(R) > 0$ then $R_*(s) > R$. From this observation and (4.5), we deduce that for any $R > 1$ there exists $s_0 \in (0, 1)$ such that if $s \in (0, s_0)$ then $R_*(s) > R$. This entails (4.2) and concludes the proof of Lemma 4.1. \square

With this preliminary work, we are now ready to complete the proof of Theorem 1.7.

Proof of Theorem 1.7. Let R_* be the radius arising from Lemma 4.1 and note that, by scaling, for any $r > 0$,

$$\mathcal{H}_{B_{R_*r} \setminus B_r}^s(x) = r^{-s} \mathcal{H}_{B_{R_*} \setminus B_1}^s\left(\frac{x}{r}\right) = 0, \quad \text{for all } x \in \partial B_r. \quad (4.8)$$

We also claim that there exists $s_0 \in (0, 1)$ such that for all $s \in (0, s_0)$ there exists $r \in (1/R_*, 1)$ such that

$$c_{n,s} \int_{B_1} \frac{\chi_{(B_{R_*r} \setminus B_r)^c}(y) - \chi_{B_{R_*r} \setminus B_r}(y)}{|x - y|^{n+s}} dy = 0, \quad \text{for all } x \in \partial B_{R_*r}. \quad (4.9)$$

Notice that, by symmetry, (4.9) is established if we show that

$$c_{n,s} \int_{B_1} \frac{\chi_{(B_{R_*r} \setminus B_r)^c}(y) - \chi_{B_{R_*r} \setminus B_r}(y)}{|R_*r e_1 - y|^{n+s}} dy = 0. \quad (4.10)$$

To check this, we define

$$g_s(r) := \int_{B_1} \frac{\chi_{(B_{R_*r} \setminus B_r)^c}(y) - \chi_{B_{R_*r} \setminus B_r}(y)}{|R_*r e_1 - y|^{n+s}} dy = \int_{B_1} \frac{\chi_{B_r}(y) - \chi_{B_r^c}(y)}{|R_*r e_1 - y|^{n+s}} dy$$

and we see that

$$\lim_{r \nearrow 1} g_s(r) = \int_{B_1} \frac{\chi_{B_1}(y) - \chi_{B_1^c}(y)}{|R_*r e_1 - y|^{n+s}} dy = \int_{B_1} \frac{dy}{|R_*r e_1 - y|^{n+s}} > 0. \quad (4.11)$$

Moreover, by (4.2) in Lemma 4.1 we have that there exists $s_0 \in (0, 1)$ such that if $s \in (0, s_0)$ then $R_* > 3$. For such values of the parameter s , we have that

$$B_{1/R_*}((1 - 1/R_*)e_1) \subset B_1 \setminus B_{1/R_*}. \quad (4.12)$$

Indeed, if $y \in B_{1/R_*}((1 - 1/R_*)e_1)$ then

$$|y| \leq \left| y - \left(1 - \frac{1}{R_*}\right) e_1 \right| + 1 - \frac{1}{R_*} < \frac{1}{R_*} + 1 - \frac{1}{R_*} = 1$$

and

$$|y| \geq \left| \left(1 - \frac{1}{R_*}\right) e_1 \right| - \frac{1}{R_*} = 1 - \frac{2}{R_*} > \frac{3}{R_*} - \frac{2}{R_*} = \frac{1}{R_*}.$$

These considerations establish (4.12).

Now, we deduce from (4.12) that

$$\begin{aligned}
\lim_{r \searrow 1/R_*} g_s(r) &= \int_{B_1} \frac{\chi_{B_{1/R_*}}(y) - \chi_{B_1 \setminus B_{1/R_*}}(y)}{|R_* r e_1 - y|^{n+s}} dy \\
&= \int_{B_1} \frac{\chi_{B_{1/R_*}}(y) - \chi_{B_{1/R_*}((1-1/R_*)e_1)}(y) - \chi_{(B_1 \setminus B_{1/R_*}) \setminus B_{1/R_*}((1-1/R_*)e_1)}(y)}{|R_* r e_1 - y|^{n+s}} dy \\
&\leq - \int_{B_1} \frac{\chi_{(B_1 \setminus B_{1/R_*}) \setminus B_{1/R_*}((1-1/R_*)e_1)}(y)}{|R_* r e_1 - y|^{n+s}} dy \\
&< 0.
\end{aligned}$$

From this and (4.11) we infer the existence of $r_* \in (1/R_*, 1)$ such that $g_s(r_*) = 0$. This completes the proof of (4.10).

Therefore, from (4.8) and (4.9) we obtain that $\partial(B_{R_* r_*} \setminus B_{r_*})$ is a free boundary s -minimal surface in B_1 , as desired. \square

5. THE VOLUME CONDITION AND PROOFS OF THEOREM 1.8 AND COROLLARY 1.10

Below is the simple, but instructive, proof of Theorem 1.8.

Proof of Theorem 1.8. We point out that $\partial E \cap \Omega^c$ is unbounded, and we take a sequence $x_k \in \partial E \cap \Omega^c$ such that $|x_k| \rightarrow +\infty$ as $k \rightarrow +\infty$.

Multiplying the free boundary condition (1.2) by $|x_k|^{n+s}$, we find that

$$\int_{\Omega} \frac{|x_k|^{n+s}}{|x_k - y|^{n+s}} (\chi_{E^c}(y) - \chi_E(y)) dy = 0.$$

Thus, by the Dominated Convergence Theorem, we obtain that

$$\int_{\Omega} (\chi_{E^c}(y) - \chi_E(y)) dy = 0,$$

which concludes the proof. \square

The work performed so far also allows us to establish Corollary 1.10.

Proof of Corollary 1.10. By the expansion (1.12) it is evident that $C_s^{2,1}$ does not satisfy the volume condition (1.10) in any ball B_R when s is close to 1, and therefore it cannot be a free boundary s -minimal surface in B_R , thanks to Theorem 1.8.

We now check that the catenoids F_s are not free boundary s -minimal surfaces in any ball B_R when s is close to 1.

To this aim, we argue by contradiction and suppose that there exist sequences $s_k \nearrow 1$ and $R_k > 0$ such that F_{s_k} is a free boundary s_k -minimal surface in B_{R_k} .

We point out that

$$F_{s_k} \text{ converges locally uniformly to a classical catenoid } F_* \text{ as } k \rightarrow +\infty. \quad (5.1)$$

FIGURE 3. The catenoid does not split any ball in two parts with equal volume. The volume in the blue part is fully compensated by the volume in the dark grey part, with a positive remainder in light grey.

Moreover, since ∂F_{s_k} is unbounded, we are in the position of applying Theorem 1.8. In this way, we obtain from the volume condition (1.10) that

$$\mathcal{H}^n(F_{s_k} \cap B_{R_k}) = \mathcal{H}^n(F_{s_k}^c \cap B_{R_k}). \quad (5.2)$$

We now claim that

$$\inf_{k \in \mathbb{N}} R_k > 0. \quad (5.3)$$

Indeed, suppose by contradiction that, up to a subsequence,

$$R_k \searrow 0 \quad (5.4)$$

and let $\epsilon > 0$ so that

$$B_r \cap \bigcup_{x \in \partial F_*} B_\epsilon(x) = \emptyset \quad (5.5)$$

for some $r > 0$ (that is, ϵ is so small that the ϵ -fattening of the catenoid surface ∂F_* does not meet the origin).

In light of (5.1), for k sufficiently large, we can also suppose that the distance between $\partial F_{s_k} \cap B_1$ and $\partial F_* \cap B_1$ is less than ϵ . Therefore, by (5.5),

$$B_r \cap \partial F_{s_k} = \emptyset.$$

Since, by (5.4), we know that $R_k < r$ for large k , we conclude that

$$B_{R_k} \cap \partial F_{s_k} = \emptyset.$$

As a consequence, one of the sides of (5.2) is null, and the other strictly positive. This is a contradiction and the proof of (5.3) is thereby complete.

Next, we claim that

$$\sup_{k \in \mathbb{N}} R_k < +\infty. \quad (5.6)$$

Indeed, suppose by contradiction that $R_k \rightarrow +\infty$. Recall that by the construction in [DPW18, Theorem 1], for s sufficiently close to 1, the fractional catenoid F_s is the set described as $\{x = (x', x_3) : |x_3| < f(|x'|)\}$, being $|x'| = \sqrt{x_1^2 + x_2^2}$, and

$$f(r) = \begin{cases} \log(r + \sqrt{r^2 - 1}) + O\left(\frac{r\sqrt{1-s}}{|\log(1-s)|}\right) & \text{if } r < (1-s)^{-1/2}, \\ r\sqrt{1-s} + O\left(\frac{r\sqrt{1-s}}{|\log(1-s)|}\right) & \text{if } r \geq (1-s)^{-1/2}. \end{cases} \quad (5.7)$$

Note that, without loss of generality, we can assume that the catenoid F_{s_k} is determined exactly by (5.7) (and not by its rescaling), since otherwise one can take a multiple of F_{s_k} that is determined by (5.7) and that is a free boundary s_k -minimal surface in a rescaling of B_{R_k} .

Now, since F_{s_k} is a free boundary s_k -minimal surface in B_{R_k} , we have that $\tilde{F}_{s_k} := R_k^{-1}F_{s_k}$ is a free boundary s_k -minimal surface in B_1 . Hence, by the expansion (5.7), we have that \tilde{F}_{s_k} is described by $\{y = (y', y_3) \in B_1 : |y_3| < f_k(|y'|)\}$, where

$$f_k(|y'|) = \begin{cases} R_k^{-1} \log\left(R_k|y'| + \sqrt{R_k^2|y'|^2 - 1}\right) + O\left(\frac{|y'|\sqrt{1-s_k}}{|\log(1-s_k)|}\right) & \text{if } |y'| < R_k^{-1}(1-s_k)^{-1/2}, \\ |y'|\sqrt{1-s_k} + O\left(\frac{|y'|\sqrt{1-s_k}}{|\log(1-s_k)|}\right) & \text{if } |y'| \geq R_k^{-1}(1-s_k)^{-1/2}. \end{cases}$$

Note that f_k is a sequence of functions converging uniformly to 0 in $B'_1 = \{|y'| < 1\}$, thus violating (5.2). This contradiction establishes (5.6).

As a consequence of (5.3) and (5.6), up to choosing a subsequence, we can assume that $R_k \rightarrow R_* \in (0, +\infty)$. Then, in light of (5.1), we have that F_{s_k} converges to F_* in B_{R_*} . This is impossible since F_* does not satisfy (1.10) in any ball, see Figure 3. \square

6. STICKINESS, BOUNDARY REGULARITY AND PROOFS OF THEOREMS 1.17 AND 1.18

This section is devoted to the boundary analysis of free boundary nonlocal minimal surfaces, namely the stickiness statement in Theorem 1.17 and the boundary behaviour in Theorem 1.18.

Proof of Theorem 1.17. Up to a rigid motion, we can suppose by contradiction that E sticks to Ω from outside at $0 \in \partial E \cap \partial\Omega$. Namely, there exists $\rho > 0$ such that

$$\begin{aligned} & \text{either } \Omega \cap B_\rho \subset E \text{ and } \Omega^c \cap B_\rho \cap E \neq \emptyset \\ & \text{or } \Omega \cap B_\rho \subset E^c \text{ and } \Omega^c \cap B_\rho \cap E^c \neq \emptyset. \end{aligned} \quad (6.1)$$

In both cases, we have that there exists a sequence of points $\{x_k\} \subset \partial E \cap \overline{\Omega}^c$ with $x_k \searrow 0$ and

$$\int_{\Omega} \frac{\chi_{E^c}(y) - \chi_E(y)}{|x_k - y|^{n+s}} dy = 0. \quad (6.2)$$

Suppose that the first situation in (6.1) occurs (the other one being analogous). In this case, we deduce from (6.2) that

$$\int_{\Omega \cap B_\rho} \frac{dy}{|x_k - y|^{n+s}} = \int_{\Omega \cap B_\rho} \frac{\chi_E(y) - \chi_{E^c}(y)}{|x_k - y|^{n+s}} dy = \int_{\Omega \cap B_\rho^c} \frac{\chi_{E^c}(y) - \chi_E(y)}{|x_k - y|^{n+s}} dy. \quad (6.3)$$

Moreover, for k large enough, we have that $x_k \in B_{\rho/2}$. Therefore, if $y \in \Omega \cap B_\rho^c$,

$$|x_k - y| \geq |y| - |x_k| \geq |y| - \frac{|y|}{2} = \frac{|y|}{2}.$$

As a consequence,

$$\left| \int_{\Omega \cap B_\rho^c} \frac{\chi_{E^c}(y) - \chi_E(y)}{|x_k - y|^{n+s}} dy \right| \leq 2 \int_{\Omega \cap B_\rho^c} \frac{dy}{|x_k - y|^{n+s}} \leq 2^{n+s+1} \int_{\Omega \cap B_\rho^c} \frac{dy}{|y|^{n+s}} \leq C,$$

for some $C > 0$ independent of k .

From this and (6.3) we infer that, for k large enough,

$$\int_{\Omega \cap B_\rho} \frac{dy}{|x_k - y|^{n+s}} \leq C.$$

Then, by Fatou's Lemma,

$$\int_{\Omega \cap B_\rho} \frac{dy}{|y|^{n+s}} \leq \lim_{k \rightarrow +\infty} \int_{\Omega \cap B_\rho} \frac{dy}{|x_k - y|^{n+s}} \leq C. \quad (6.4)$$

On the other hand, we have that

$$\int_{\Omega \cap B_\rho} \frac{dy}{|y|^{n+s}} = +\infty,$$

in contradiction with (6.4). \square

Before proving Theorem 1.18, we need some preliminary statements.

We first show that corners produce an infinite nonlocal mean curvature. Some care is needed for a statement of this type, because of course symmetric grids may have vanishing mean curvature. Also, in our setting the nonlocal mean curvature is not computed exactly at the corner, but only arbitrarily close to it, and this produces some technical issues in the integral calculations.

The result that we need goes as follows:

Lemma 6.1. *Let $E \subset \mathbb{R}^n$, with $0 \in \partial E$. Let $\alpha \in (s, 1]$ and $T : \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^n$ be a diffeomorphism of class $C^{1,\alpha}$ with $T(0) = 0$, $DT(0) = \text{Id}$, and such that $T(B_r) = B_r$ and $T(E \cap B_r) = E_1 \cup E_2$, where*

$$E_1 := \{x \in B_r \text{ s.t. } x_1 \geq 0 \text{ and } \omega_1 \cdot x < 0\}$$

and

$$E_2 := \{x \in B_r \text{ s.t. } x_1 \leq 0 \text{ and } \omega_2 \cdot x < 0\},$$

for some unit vectors $\omega_1, \omega_2 \in \mathbb{R}^n$ (see Figure 4).

FIGURE 4. The sets E_1 and E_2 from Lemma 6.1

Suppose that¹

$$\{x \in B_r \text{ s.t. } x_1 \leq 0 \text{ and } \omega_1 \cdot x < 0\} \subset E_2. \quad (6.5)$$

Then, either $\omega_1 = \omega_2$ or

$$\lim_{T(\partial E_1) \ni x \rightarrow 0} \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} \frac{\chi_{E^c}(y) - \chi_E(y)}{|x - y|^{n+s}} dy = -\infty. \quad (6.6)$$

Proof. We point out that, for all $x, y \in B_r$,

$$|T(x) - T(y) - (x - y)| = \left| \int_0^1 \left(DT(tx + (1-t)y) - \text{Id} \right) (x - y) dt \right| \leq C|x - y|^{1+\alpha},$$

for some $C > 0$, and, in a similar vein, up to freely renaming C ,

$$|T^{-1}(X) - T^{-1}(Y) - (X - Y)| \leq C|X - Y|^{1+\alpha}. \quad (6.7)$$

We also claim that, for all $a, b \geq 0$ and all $\gamma \geq 1$,

$$|a^\gamma - b^\gamma| \leq \gamma(a + b)^{\gamma-1}|a - b|. \quad (6.8)$$

To check this, without loss of generality, we can assume that $a > 0$ and $b > 0$, otherwise the result is obvious, and, up to swapping a and b , that $a \geq b$. Then, we let $c := a - b \geq 0$ and we find that

$$\begin{aligned} |a^\gamma - b^\gamma| &= (b + c)^\gamma - b^\gamma = \gamma \int_0^c (b + t)^{\gamma-1} dt \leq \gamma(b + c)^{\gamma-1}c \\ &= \gamma a^{\gamma-1}(a - b) \leq \gamma(a + b)^{\gamma-1}|a - b|, \end{aligned}$$

¹Up to complementary sets, Lemma 6.1 has a similar statement in which condition (6.5) is replaced by

$$\{x \in B_r \text{ s.t. } x_1 \geq 0 \text{ and } \omega_2 \cdot x < 0\} \subset E_1$$

and the corresponding thesis in (6.6) becomes

$$\lim_{T(\partial E_1) \ni x \rightarrow 0} \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} \frac{\chi_{E^c}(y) - \chi_E(y)}{|x - y|^{n+s}} dy = +\infty.$$

which establishes (6.8).

By (6.7) and (6.8), used here with $a := |X - Y|$, $b := |T^{-1}(X) - T^{-1}(Y)|$ and $\gamma := n + s$, we gather that

$$\begin{aligned}
& \left| |X - Y|^{n+s} - |T^{-1}(X) - T^{-1}(Y)|^{n+s} \right| \\
& \leq (n + s) \left(|X - Y| + |T^{-1}(X) - T^{-1}(Y)| \right)^{n+s-1} \left| |X - Y| - |T^{-1}(X) - T^{-1}(Y)| \right| \\
& \leq C |X - Y|^{n+s-1} \left| |X - Y| - |T^{-1}(X) - T^{-1}(Y)| \right| \\
& \leq C |X - Y|^{n+s-1} |(X - Y) - (T^{-1}(X) - T^{-1}(Y))| \\
& \leq C |X - Y|^{n+s+\alpha} \\
& \leq C |T^{-1}(X) - T^{-1}(Y)|^{n+s} |X - Y|^\alpha.
\end{aligned} \tag{6.9}$$

Now, given $x \in B_r$, we use the notation $X := T(x)$ and

$$\Phi(X, Y) := \frac{|X - Y|^{n+s}}{|T^{-1}(X) - T^{-1}(Y)|^{n+s}}.$$

It follows from (6.9) that

$$|\Phi(X, Y) - 1| = \left| \frac{|X - Y|^{n+s} - |T^{-1}(X) - T^{-1}(Y)|^{n+s}}{|T^{-1}(X) - T^{-1}(Y)|^{n+s}} \right| \leq C |X - Y|^\alpha.$$

Hence, if $E_* := E_1 \cup E_2$, we find that, for all $x \in B_r$,

$$\begin{aligned}
\Xi(x) &:= \int_{B_r} \frac{\chi_{E^c}(y) - \chi_E(y)}{|x - y|^{n+s}} dy - \int_{B_r} \left(\chi_{E_*^c}(Y) - \chi_{E_*}(Y) \right) \frac{|\det DT^{-1}(Y)|}{|X - Y|^{n+s}} dY \\
&= \int_{B_r} \left(\chi_{E_*^c}(Y) - \chi_{E_*}(Y) \right) \frac{|\det DT^{-1}(Y)| dY}{|T^{-1}(X) - T^{-1}(Y)|^{n+s}} \\
&\quad - \int_{B_r} \left(\chi_{E_*^c}(Y) - \chi_{E_*}(Y) \right) \frac{|\det DT^{-1}(Y)|}{|X - Y|^{n+s}} dY \\
&= \int_{B_r} \frac{\chi_{E_*^c}(Y) - \chi_{E_*}(Y)}{|X - Y|^{n+s}} \left(\Phi(X, Y) - 1 \right) |\det DT^{-1}(Y)| dY
\end{aligned}$$

and consequently

$$|\Xi(x)| \leq C \int_{B_r} \frac{|\Phi(X, Y) - 1|}{|X - Y|^{n+s}} dY \leq C \int_{B_r} \frac{|X - Y|^\alpha}{|X - Y|^{n+s}} dY \leq Cr^{\alpha-s}. \tag{6.10}$$

We let

$$G := \{x \in \mathbb{R}^n \text{ s.t. } \omega_1 \cdot x < 0\}$$

and we claim that

$$\left| \int_{B_r} \left(\chi_{G^c}(Y) - \chi_G(Y) \right) \frac{|\det DT^{-1}(Y)|}{|X - Y|^{n+s}} dY \right| \leq Cr^{\alpha-s}. \tag{6.11}$$

To check this, we observe that, by symmetry,

$$\int_{B_r} \left(\chi_{G^c}(Y) - \chi_G(Y) \right) \frac{dY}{|X - Y|^{n+s}} = 0$$

and accordingly

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \int_{B_r} \left(\chi_{G^c}(Y) - \chi_G(Y) \right) \frac{|\det DT^{-1}(Y)|}{|X - Y|^{n+s}} dY \right| \\ &= \left| \int_{B_r} \left(\chi_{G^c}(Y) - \chi_G(Y) \right) \frac{|\det DT^{-1}(Y)| - |\det DT^{-1}(X)|}{|X - Y|^{n+s}} dY \right| \\ &\leq \int_{B_r} \frac{||\det DT^{-1}(Y)| - |\det DT^{-1}(X)||}{|X - Y|^{n+s}} dY \\ &\leq C \int_{B_r} \frac{dY}{|X - Y|^{n+s-\alpha}} \\ &\leq Cr^{\alpha-s} \end{aligned}$$

and this gives (6.11).

Now suppose that $\omega_1 \neq \omega_2$. Then, the cone

$$F := \{x \in B_r \text{ s.t. } x_1 \leq 0 \text{ and } \omega_2 \cdot x < 0 \leq \omega_1 \cdot x\}$$

has positive measure and therefore, up to taking r smaller if needed, changing variables $Z := \frac{Y}{|X|}$, and setting $\widehat{X} := \frac{X}{|X|}$,

$$\int_{F \cap B_r} \frac{|\det DT^{-1}(Y)|}{|X - Y|^{n+s}} dY \geq c \int_{F \cap B_r} \frac{dY}{|X - Y|^{n+s}} = \frac{c}{|X|^s} \int_{B_r/|X| \cap F} \frac{dZ}{|\widehat{X} - Z|^{n+s}} \geq \frac{c}{|X|^s},$$

as long as $|X|$ is small enough (possibly with respect to r), and up to renaming $c > 0$.

From this, (6.10) and (6.11), writing $E_* = (F \cup G) \cap B_r$, we deduce that

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_{B_r} \frac{\chi_{E^c}(y) - \chi_E(y)}{|x - y|^{n+s}} dy \\ &= \Xi(x) + \int_{B_r} \left(\chi_{E_*^c}(Y) - \chi_{E_*}(Y) \right) \frac{|\det DT^{-1}(Y)|}{|X - Y|^{n+s}} dY \\ &= \Xi(x) + \int_{B_r} \left(\chi_{G_*^c}(Y) - \chi_{G_*}(Y) \right) \frac{|\det DT^{-1}(Y)|}{|X - Y|^{n+s}} dY - 2 \int_{F \cap B_r} \frac{|\det DT^{-1}(Y)|}{|X - Y|^{n+s}} dY \\ &\leq Cr^{\alpha-s} - \frac{c}{|X|^s}. \end{aligned} \tag{6.12}$$

Also, if $|x| \leq \frac{r}{2}$,

$$\left| \int_{B_r^c} \frac{\chi_{E^c}(y) - \chi_E(y)}{|x - y|^{n+s}} dy \right| \leq \int_{B_r^c} \frac{dy}{|x - y|^{n+s}} \leq C \int_{B_r^c} \frac{dy}{|y|^{n+s}} \leq \frac{C}{r^s}.$$

FIGURE 5. The setting of Lemma 6.2

Combining this and (6.12), we conclude that

$$\begin{aligned} \lim_{T(\partial E_1) \ni x \rightarrow 0} \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} \frac{\chi_{E^c}(y) - \chi_E(y)}{|x - y|^{n+s}} dy &= \lim_{E_1 \ni X = T(x) \rightarrow 0} \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} \frac{\chi_{E^c}(y) - \chi_E(y)}{|x - y|^{n+s}} dy \\ &\leq \lim_{E_1 \ni X = T(x) \rightarrow 0} \frac{C}{r^s} + Cr^{\alpha-s} - \frac{c}{|X|^s} = -\infty, \end{aligned}$$

as desired. \square

Below is a useful variation of Lemma 6.1 estimating integral contributions in Ω :

Lemma 6.2. *Let E and Ω be as above and let*

$$\vartheta \in \left(-\frac{\pi}{2}, \frac{\pi}{2}\right). \quad (6.13)$$

Assume that $0 \in \partial E \cap \partial \Omega$ and that there exist $r > 0$ and a diffeomorphism $T : \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^n$ of class $C^{1,\alpha}$, with $T(0) = 0$, $DT(0) = \text{Id}$, $T(B_r) = B_r$, $T(B_r \cap \Omega) = B_r \cap \{x_1 > 0\}$ and

$$T(E \cap B_r) = \{x \in B_r \text{ s.t. } \omega \cdot x < 0\} \quad (6.14)$$

for some unit vector $\omega = (-\sin \vartheta, 0, \dots, 0, \cos \vartheta)$.

Let $\rho_k \in (0, \frac{r}{2})$ be an infinitesimal sequence and $\varpi := (-\cos \vartheta, 0, \dots, 0, -\sin \vartheta)$ (see Figure 5). Let also $x_k := T^{-1}(\rho_k \varpi)$.

Then, x_k is infinitesimal as $k \rightarrow +\infty$. Also, for large k ,

$$x_k \in (\partial E) \cap \overline{\Omega}^c. \quad (6.15)$$

Moreover, if $\vartheta \in (0, \frac{\pi}{2})$, then

$$\lim_{k \rightarrow +\infty} \int_{\Omega} \frac{\chi_{E^c}(y) - \chi_E(y)}{|x_k - y|^{n+s}} dy = -\infty. \quad (6.16)$$

Similarly, if $\vartheta \in (-\frac{\pi}{2}, 0)$, then

$$\lim_{k \rightarrow +\infty} \int_{\Omega} \frac{\chi_{E^c}(y) - \chi_E(y)}{|x_k - y|^{n+s}} dy = +\infty. \quad (6.17)$$

Proof. We remark that $\omega \cdot \varpi = 0$ and therefore, by (6.14), for large k we have that

$$T(x_k) = \rho_k \varpi \in \{x \in B_r \text{ s.t. } \omega \cdot x = 0\} = T(\partial E \cap B_r). \quad (6.18)$$

Furthermore, if $e_1 := (1, 0, \dots, 0)$, we see that $e_1 \cdot \varpi = -\cos \vartheta < 0$, owing to (6.13). Accordingly, for large k , we have that

$$T(x_k) = \rho_k \varpi \in \{x \in B_r \text{ s.t. } e_1 \cdot x < 0\} = T(\overline{\Omega}^c \cap B_r).$$

From this and (6.18), we obtain (6.15), as desired.

Now we use the notation $Y := T(y)$ and we compute that

$$\begin{aligned} \Upsilon_k &:= \int_{B_r \cap \Omega} \frac{\chi_{E^c}(y) - \chi_E(y)}{|x_k - y|^{n+s}} dy \\ &= \int_{B_r \cap \{Y_1 > 0\} \cap \{\omega \cdot Y > 0\}} \frac{|\det DT^{-1}(Y)| dY}{|T^{-1}(\rho_k \varpi) - T^{-1}(Y)|^{n+s}} \\ &\quad - \int_{B_r \cap \{Y_1 > 0\} \cap \{\omega \cdot Y < 0\}} \frac{|\det DT^{-1}(Y)| dY}{|T^{-1}(\rho_k \varpi) - T^{-1}(Y)|^{n+s}}. \end{aligned}$$

Substituting for $Z := \frac{Y}{\rho_k}$, we conclude that

$$\begin{aligned} \rho_k^s \Upsilon_k &= \int_{B_{r/\rho_k} \cap \{Z_1 > 0\} \cap \{\omega \cdot Z > 0\}} \frac{|\det DT^{-1}(\rho_k Z)| dZ}{|\rho_k^{-1} T^{-1}(\rho_k \varpi) - \rho_k^{-1} T^{-1}(\rho_k Z)|^{n+s}} \\ &\quad - \int_{B_{r/\rho_k} \cap \{Z_1 > 0\} \cap \{\omega \cdot Z < 0\}} \frac{|\det DT^{-1}(\rho_k Z)| dZ}{|\rho_k^{-1} T^{-1}(\rho_k \varpi) - \rho_k^{-1} T^{-1}(\rho_k Z)|^{n+s}} =: \Xi_k. \end{aligned} \quad (6.19)$$

We stress that

$$\rho_k^{-1} T^{-1}(\rho_k Z) = \rho_k^{-1} \left(\rho_k DT^{-1}(0)Z + O(\rho_k^{1+\alpha}) \right) = Z + O(\rho_k^\alpha),$$

as well as $\rho_k^{-1} T^{-1}(\rho_k \varpi) = \varpi + O(\rho_k^\alpha)$.

Hence, recalling (6.13),

$$\lim_{k \rightarrow +\infty} e_1 \rho_k^{-1} T^{-1}(\rho_k \varpi) = e_1 \cdot \varpi = -\cos \vartheta$$

and thus, for large k , we have that $e_1 \rho_k^{-1} T^{-1}(\rho_k \varpi) \leq -\frac{\cos \vartheta}{2} < 0$.

This allows us to use the Dominated Convergence Theorem and deduce that

$$\lim_{k \rightarrow +\infty} \Xi_k = \int_{\{Z_1 > 0\} \cap \{\omega \cdot Z > 0\}} \frac{dZ}{|\varpi - Z|^{n+s}} - \int_{\{Z_1 > 0\} \cap \{\omega \cdot Z < 0\}} \frac{dZ}{|\varpi - Z|^{n+s}}. \quad (6.20)$$

We now consider the reflection \mathcal{R} through the hyperplane normal to ω , namely

$$W := \mathcal{R}(Z) = Z - 2(\omega \cdot Z)\omega.$$

Thus, since $Z = W - 2(\omega \cdot W)\omega$ and $\omega \cdot \varpi = 0$,

$$\begin{aligned} |\varpi - Z|^2 &= |(\varpi - W) + 2(\omega \cdot W)\omega|^2 \\ &= |\varpi - W|^2 + 4(\omega \cdot W)^2 + 4(\omega \cdot W)(\varpi - W) \cdot \omega = |\varpi - W|^2. \end{aligned}$$

On this account,

$$\Lambda := \int_{\{Z_1 > 0\} \cap \{\omega \cdot Z > 0\}} \frac{dZ}{|\varpi - Z|^{n+s}} = \int_{\{W_1 > 2(\omega \cdot W)\omega_1\} \cap \{\omega \cdot W < 0\}} \frac{dW}{|\varpi - W|^{n+s}}. \quad (6.21)$$

Suppose now that $\vartheta \in (0, \frac{\pi}{2})$. Then, $\omega_1 < 0$. Hence,

$$\{W_1 > 2(\omega \cdot W)\omega_1\} \cap \{\omega \cdot W < 0\} \subset \{W_1 > 0\}.$$

It follows from this observation, (6.20) and (6.21) that

$$\begin{aligned} \lim_{k \rightarrow +\infty} \Xi_k &= \Lambda - \int_{\{Z_1 > 0\} \cap \{\omega \cdot Z < 0\}} \frac{dZ}{|\varpi - Z|^{n+s}} \\ &= - \int_{\{W_1 \in (0, 2(\omega \cdot W)\omega_1]\} \cap \{\omega \cdot W < 0\}} \frac{dW}{|\varpi - W|^{n+s}}, \end{aligned}$$

which is a strictly negative quantity.

This and (6.19) yield that

$$\lim_{k \rightarrow +\infty} \Upsilon_k = -\infty. \quad (6.22)$$

Also, since $x_k \in B_{r/2}$,

$$\left| \int_{B_r^c \cap \Omega} \frac{\chi_{E^c}(y) - \chi_E(y)}{|x_k - y|^{n+s}} dy \right| \leq \int_{B_r^c} \frac{dy}{|x_k - y|^{n+s}} \leq C \int_{B_r^c} \frac{dy}{|y|^{n+s}} \leq \frac{C}{r^s}.$$

The proof of (6.16) is now completed, thanks to the latter observation and (6.22).

The proof of (6.17) is alike. \square

We now recall an easy observation regarding smooth functions:

Lemma 6.3. *Let B be a ball in \mathbb{R}^N , centered at the origin. Let $\varphi_1, \varphi_2 \in C^{1,\alpha}(B)$, for some $\alpha \in (0, 1]$.*

Let

$$\varphi(x_1, \dots, x_N) := \begin{cases} \varphi_1(x_1, \dots, x_N) & \text{if } x_1 \geq 0, \\ \varphi_2(x_1, \dots, x_N) & \text{if } x_1 < 0. \end{cases} \quad (6.23)$$

Assume that, for all $(0, \dots, x_{N-1}, x_N) \in B$,

$$\varphi_1(0, \dots, x_{N-1}, x_N) = \varphi_2(0, \dots, x_{N-1}, x_N) \quad (6.24)$$

and, for all $j \in \{1, \dots, N\}$,

$$\partial_j \varphi_1(0, \dots, x_{N-1}, x_N) = \partial_j \varphi_2(0, \dots, x_{N-1}, x_N). \quad (6.25)$$

Then, $\varphi \in C^{1,\alpha}(B)$.

Proof. We stress that φ is continuous in B , thanks to (6.24).

We also have that φ is differentiable in B , with

$$\partial_j \varphi(x_1, \dots, x_N) = \begin{cases} \partial_j \varphi_1(x_1, \dots, x_N) & \text{if } x_1 \geq 0, \\ \partial_j \varphi_2(x_1, \dots, x_N) & \text{if } x_1 < 0. \end{cases} \quad (6.26)$$

This follows from (6.23) when $x_1 \neq 0$, hence we focus on the case $x_1 = 0$.

For this, we use (6.25) and we see that, as $h = (h_1, \dots, h_N) \rightarrow 0$,

$$\begin{aligned} & \varphi(h_1, x_2 + h_2, \dots, x_N + h_N) - \varphi(0, x_2, \dots, x_N) \\ &= \begin{cases} \varphi_1(h_1, x_2 + h_2, \dots, x_N + h_N) - \varphi_1(0, x_2, \dots, x_N) & \text{if } h_1 > 0, \\ \varphi_2(h_1, x_2 + h_2, \dots, x_N + h_N) - \varphi_2(0, x_2, \dots, x_N) & \text{if } h_1 < 0, \end{cases} \\ &= \begin{cases} \nabla\varphi_1(0, x_2, \dots, x_N) \cdot h + o(h) & \text{if } h_1 > 0, \\ \nabla\varphi_2(0, x_2, \dots, x_N) \cdot h + o(h) & \text{if } h_1 < 0, \end{cases} \\ &= \nabla\varphi_1(0, x_2, \dots, x_N) \cdot h + o(h), \end{aligned}$$

from which the proof of (6.26) follows.

Now, to complete the proof of (6.3), we check that, for all $x = (x_1, \dots, x_N)$ and $y = (y_1, \dots, y_N)$ in B , with $x \neq y$,

$$\frac{|\nabla\varphi(x) - \nabla\varphi(y)|}{|x - y|^\alpha} \leq C \max \{ \|\varphi_1\|_{C^{1,\alpha}(B)}, \|\varphi_2\|_{C^{1,\alpha}(B)} \}, \quad (6.27)$$

for some $C \geq 1$.

When $x_1 > 0$ and $y_1 > 0$, as well as when $x_1 < 0$ and $y_1 < 0$, the claim in (6.27) is a direct consequence of (6.26) and the regularity assumption on φ_1 and φ_2 .

Hence, we can restrict to the case in which $x_1 > 0 > y_1$. In this case, we pick $z = (0, z_2, \dots, z_N)$ in the segment joining x to y and we remark that $|x - y| = |x - z| + |z - y|$. Therefore, by (6.26),

$$\begin{aligned} |\nabla\varphi(x) - \nabla\varphi(y)| &\leq |\nabla\varphi(x) - \nabla\varphi(z)| + |\nabla\varphi(z) - \nabla\varphi(y)| \\ &= |\nabla\varphi_1(x) - \nabla\varphi_1(z)| + |\nabla\varphi_2(z) - \nabla\varphi_2(y)| \\ &\leq \|\varphi_1\|_{C^{1,\alpha}(B)} |x - z|^\alpha + \|\varphi_2\|_{C^{1,\alpha}(B)} |z - y|^\alpha \\ &\leq \max \{ \|\varphi_1\|_{C^{1,\alpha}(B)}, \|\varphi_2\|_{C^{1,\alpha}(B)} \} (|x - z|^\alpha + |z - y|^\alpha) \\ &\leq \max \{ \|\varphi_1\|_{C^{1,\alpha}(B)}, \|\varphi_2\|_{C^{1,\alpha}(B)} \} (|x - y|^\alpha + |x - y|^\alpha), \end{aligned}$$

and (6.27) plainly follows. \square

With the preliminary work done so far we can now complete the proof of Theorem 1.18.

Proof of Theorem 1.18. Given $x_1, x_n \in \mathbb{R}$, we let

$$\left(-\frac{\pi}{2}, \frac{\pi}{2}\right) \ni \vartheta \longmapsto f(\vartheta) := -x_1 \tan \vartheta + x_n$$

and we observe that

$$f \text{ is nondecreasing when } x_1 \leq 0 \text{ and nonincreasing when } x_1 \geq 0. \quad (6.28)$$

We claim that when $\vartheta_1 > \vartheta_2$ we have that

$$\{x \in B_r \text{ s.t. } x_1 \leq 0 \text{ and } \omega_1 \cdot x < 0\} \subset \{x \in B_r \text{ s.t. } x_1 \leq 0 \text{ and } \omega_2 \cdot x < 0\} \quad (6.29)$$

and when $\vartheta_1 < \vartheta_2$ we have that

$$\{x \in B_r \text{ s.t. } x_1 \geq 0 \text{ and } \omega_2 \cdot x < 0\} \subset \{x \in B_r \text{ s.t. } x_1 \geq 0 \text{ and } \omega_1 \cdot x < 0\}. \quad (6.30)$$

Indeed, suppose that $x_1 \leq 0$ and $\vartheta_1 > \vartheta_2$. Then, since $\cos \vartheta > 0$, we deduce from (6.28) that

$$\begin{aligned} \omega_1 \cdot x &= -x_1 \sin \vartheta_1 + x_n \cos \vartheta_1 = f(\vartheta_1) \cos \vartheta_1 \geq f(\vartheta_2) \cos \vartheta_1 \\ &= f(\vartheta_2) \cos \vartheta_2 \frac{\cos \vartheta_1}{\cos \vartheta_2} = \omega_2 \cdot x \frac{\cos \vartheta_1}{\cos \vartheta_2} \end{aligned}$$

and (6.29) follows.

Similarly, if $\vartheta_1 < \vartheta_2$ one obtains (6.30).

Now we claim that

$$\vartheta_1 = \vartheta_2. \tag{6.31}$$

For this, we argue by contradiction. Namely, suppose that the claim in (6.31) does not hold. Then, either $\vartheta_1 > \vartheta_2$ or $\vartheta_1 < \vartheta_2$. Accordingly, either (6.29) holds true (and thus we can use Lemma 6.1) or (6.30) is satisfied (and in this case we can rely on footnote 1 on page 36). In any case,

$$\left| \lim_{(\partial E) \cap \Omega \ni x \rightarrow 0} \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} \frac{\chi_{E^c}(y) - \chi_E(y)}{|x - y|^{n+s}} dy \right| = +\infty.$$

This violates condition (1.1) (recall Theorem 1.2) and this proves (6.31).

Hence, we set $\vartheta := \vartheta_1 = \vartheta_2$ and we have that E is of class $C^{1,\alpha}$ in the vicinity of the origin (see Lemma 6.3). As a consequence, to complete the proof of Theorem 1.18, it remains to check that $\vartheta = 0$.

Suppose not. Then, we can use Lemma 6.2 and deduce from either (6.16) or (6.17) that

$$\left| \lim_{k \rightarrow +\infty} \int_{\Omega} \frac{\chi_{E^c}(y) - \chi_E(y)}{|x_k - y|^{n+s}} dy \right| = +\infty.$$

This is in contradiction with condition (1.2) (recall Theorem 1.2) and the proof of Theorem 1.18 is complete. \square

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